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Master's thesis

THE MEDIA'S WAR

To what extent might the media influence users' behaviour and attitudes through news, advertising and cultural representations, with a focus on media effects in relation to media coverage of the Israel/Palestine conflict?

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× THE MEDIA'S WAR

Det er et slag i ansigtet på dem i regionen, som ønsker at finde

Firas Abiad
Sundhedsminister, Libanon

BBC VERIFY

Forsker om Hamas:
»Grusomhederne, der fandt sted, havde en ondskab over sig, som er næsten umulig at oppe

For Magnus Ranstorp overgår grusomhederne under Hamas' angreb 7. oktober alt, hvad han tidligere har

Hizbollah anklager Israel

Dagbladet Information
7 t. ·
»Hvis jøderne ønsker at sende antisemitisme på retræte, så må de – i selvransagelser – tage et reelt opgør med den israelske besættelsesmagt,« skriver Isam Bachiri i kronik.

3.543 96 123

information.dk
DEBAT: Isam B: Opgøret med antisemitisme starter hos jøderne selv

121
Synes godt om
9 kommentarer 12 delinger
Kommenter
Kopier
Del

nyheder.tv2.dk
Stor demonstration i København – tusindvis gik på gaden for våbenhvile

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1. Abstract

This thesis explores the influence of media content on user behaviour and attitudes, with a focus on understanding media effects within the context of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. Through an analysis of media coverage and public opinion during two distinct periods, the study illustrates how shifts in media representation have led to significant changes in public perception. The research employs a mixed-methods approach, integrating content analysis, surveys, and qualitative interviews, to provide a comprehensive examination of how media outlets, through their portrayal of events, actively shape societal norms and values.

The study's findings indicate that media exposure can result in both immediate and long-term impacts on audience attitudes, demonstrating potential "far-reaching" consequences beyond the initial period of media coverage. The thesis further explores how interest groups may strategically utilise these media effects to reinforce or alter public opinion, thereby influencing the wider social and cultural structures within society.

The theoretical framework is grounded in Denis McQuail's media effects theory and is further complemented by Fabian Thomas's exploration of media effect patterns, Stig Hjarvad's mediatisation theory, and Maxwell McCombs' theory of agenda-setting. Collectively, these theories provide insights into how media not only reflects but also transforms social structures and cultural norms.

Moreover, the research highlights the role of media in embedding social relations within new contexts, which can alter both individual and collective behaviours. By employing a triangulated methodology that combines quantitative and qualitative research, the study ensures a robust exploration of media's multifaceted influence on public perception.

In conclusion, this thesis contributes to the ongoing debate on media's role in contemporary society by advocating for a critical and conscious approach to media consumption. It underscores the importance of understanding media effects, particularly in how they shape public opinion and contribute to the formation of social conflicts and identity shifts. This research also suggests areas for further investigation, particularly concerning the unplanned and enduring consequences of media influence.

2. Introduction

In this thesis, I will analyse the media's representation of the conflict between Hamas and Israel, which will thus be the thesis' primary case in terms of examining the media's influence on individual attitudes.

It is my experience that the media coverage of the conflict has created a societal discussion and has perhaps even changed people's attitudes. Throughout the period from the attack on 7 October 2023, and again on 7 April 2024, until now, I have observed that people have freely spoken out about the conflict and have changed their attitudes towards it. This thesis simply measures this shift in media coverage without politicising or addressing the underlying causes.

Israel's conflict with its neighbours has been a topic of debate in the media since the establishment of the state in 1948. This continuous media coverage supports the relevance of analysing media effects related to this conflict, making it understandable and meaningful to choose this case for the study, and it seems that between the mentioned dates in this flare-up of the conflict there has been a shift in attitudes towards it.

This shift in media attitudes, from pro-Israeli to more pro-Palestinian coverage, is intriguing in a media effects context. It is precisely the role of media coverage in shaping public perception that is crucial, and this is where analysing media effects becomes particularly relevant. By highlighting this change in media coverage over time, the thesis can contribute to the understanding of how media effects influence public attitudes as the conflict evolves.

The choice of media effects as the object of the study is justified by the fact that access to Gaza has been virtually impossible for everyone, including journalists. This has forced the media to base their reporting on eyewitness accounts and secondary sources, meaning that the media effectively act as the only witnesses to what is going on. The perception of the population, including the journalist and public opinion, is therefore primarily shaped by the media, as almost no one has had access to the conflict area. This emphasises that this is a clear example of a direct media effect.

The media has thus played a central role as a disseminator of information and has greatly influenced how the Danish population perceives the conflict. This atypical case clearly illustrates how the media not only reflects reality but also shapes it by emphasising certain aspects of the conflict and downplaying others, which therefore motivates the choice of this focus for the thesis.

The primary theory will be utilised is therefore the media effects theory. This theoretical framework will be introduced as an instrument to explore and understand the dynamics of power and ideology in relation to the role of media.

We are constantly influenced by media content and live in a world saturated by media images and sounds. Politicians, governments and businesses act on the assumption that we are informed. Many people form opinions and gain information through the media, and vast

resources are spent on managing the media to achieve these effects (McQuail, 1994, p. 327).

The thesis analysis is complemented by the inclusion of concepts related to media effects, such as media effect patterns and medialisation. Medialisation is a key concept to understand in relation to the role of media in culture and society. It has been used to examine the impact of media on various phenomena, but there have not been extensive attempts to clarify its meaning (Hjarvad, 2009, p. 6).

In an era of digitalisation and a constant flow of information, the media plays a crucial role in shaping opinion in modern society. The unrestricted access to content from around the world has arguably increased the power of media to shape public space and thus individual consciousness. The study will explore how the media, through its content and representations, can influence behaviour and values in society, which will be presented through *Denis McQuail's Mass Communication Theory and Stig Hjarvad's Mediatization Theory*.

With this media effects focus, this thesis examines the underlying mechanisms and dynamics behind the media's influence on users. It also analyses how media can act as tools for interest groups to control and sometimes manipulate public perception. McQuail, who belongs to the older generation of media effects scholars, maintained the focus on media effects in the second half of the 20th century and contributed significantly to the understanding of media influence on society. *Fabian Thomas* research builds upon existing theories and represents a more recent development in media effects studies. This thesis applies McQuail's Theory of Media Effects, Hjarvad's Mediatization Theory, and Thomas' *Media Effect Patterns* as key theoretical frameworks. Thomas distinguishes between the moment a media effect first occurs and its duration over time, offering a longitudinal perspective on media influence:

When taking a longitudinal perspective on media effects, it is important to differentiate between two questions. The first question is how long it takes until a media effect can be expected to occur, i.e., the appearance of media effects. The second question is how long that media effect lasts over time, i.e., the duration of media effects (Thomas, 2022, p. 403).

For the initial content analysis and survey of the thesis, it was necessary to conduct an interview study based on the project objectives to balance the weaknesses of the quantitative studies. The aim was that the results of the content analysis and survey could be supported and validated by the interview study. This triangulation refers to the fact that quantitative and qualitative research can be combined to mutually confirm findings. In the qualitative part of the thesis, I explain the interview-based data collection using *Steinar Kvale and Svend Brinkmann's* book *Interview: The Qualitative Research Interview as a Craft*.

In addition, several technical terms and method descriptions are used, these are included in accordance with *Mikkel Fugl Eskjær and Rasmus Helle's* book *Quantitative Content Analysis* and *Alan Bryman's* book *Social Research Methods*.

Several researchers have previously documented how media act as powerful actors that shape public attitudes and political processes, including Claes H. de Vreese, Daniela

Dimitrova and Jesper Strömbäck and Peter Jacobsen and Karsten Møller . For example, Hjarvad and Kristensen's article "When media of a small nation argue for war" demonstrates the media's ability to influence public opinion through agenda-setting and framing. Their article thus supports the theoretical basis for this thesis, which examines how media coverage of the conflict between Hamas and Israel shapes perceptions and attitudes in society in accordance with the theory of medialisation (Hjarvad, 2009, pp. 5-7) (Hjarvad & Kristensen, 2014).

The media's influence on perceptions, attitudes and actions can thus be seen as a key research field in the digital age. Previously seen as neutral mediators, the media are now perceived as powerful actors that shape the collective consciousness of society. The thesis examines how media create new realities and influence social norms and political ideologies with reference to McQuail, Hjarvad, Thomas, Eskjær and Helles, Kvale and Brinkmann and Bryman. In addition, the thesis promotes critical reflection on the influence of media on behaviour and discusses how critical media consumption can strengthen democracy. This leads to the problem statement, which focuses on the role of media in modern society.

2.1 Research question

To what extent might the media influence users' behaviour and attitudes through news, advertising and cultural representations, with a focus on media effects in relation to media coverage of the Israel/Palestine conflict

Through a combination of quantitative and qualitative analyses in a longitudinal study over six months, the aim is to uncover whether the media is able to influence people's attitudes and sympathies in connection with the conflict

This thesis thus analyses the agenda-setting role of the media by examining which topics are highlighted and how these affect the perception of their importance in the public debate.

This thesis makes use of the following working questions:

- How has the media landscape changed during these periods?
- How have people's attitudes changed within the same periods?
- How can this be expressed qualitatively in an interview?

2.2 Delimitation and concept clarification

The thesis examines the media's representation of the conflict through an article analysis of news reports published in two specific periods. These periods were selected to ensure a representative sample of media coverage over time.

The chosen timeframe serves multiple purposes: analysing media coverage across two distinct periods facilitates the identification of changes and patterns in reporting. Only national newspapers are included to maintain consistency and relevance. By limiting searches to specific keywords, the analysis remains focused on the conflict between Hamas and Israel.

To ensure clarity and precision in the thesis, it is essential to define key concepts used in the analysis. In this context, "war" refers to armed conflicts between Hamas and Israel, encompassing military operations, bombardments, and other forms of armed confrontation. "Israel" refers to the state of Israel, including its government, military, and civilian population. "Gaza" refers to the Gaza Strip, primarily controlled by Hamas, encompassing both military and civilian aspects of the region. "National newspapers" refers to major Danish newspapers with broad national distribution, such as *Politiken*, *Berlingske*, and *Jyllands-Posten*.

This thesis, by utilising a carefully selected, approximately representative sample, seeks to illuminate the overall impact of media coverage on recipients' attitudes and perceptions of the conflict between Hamas and Israel. The analysis focuses on the collective portrayal of the conflict in the selected media, rather than examining individual media sources or differences between specific outlets. The objective is to identify overarching trends in Danish media coverage and its influence on audiences, regardless of variations across different media.

This approach allows for a broader understanding of media effects by prioritising the overall content and framing of media narratives rather than the political or editorial orientations of individual news sources.

Furthermore, the thesis employs several English terms where direct Danish translations would either distort meaning or hinder the overall readability and coherence of the study.

2.3 Reading guide

The thesis will use a traditional sender/receiver structure, where the meaning of the message is integrated as a central part of the analysis. This can be illustrated as follows:

Structural Composition of the Thesis in Chapters

2.4 Case description

The primary case of the thesis is the media's representation of the conflict between Hamas and Israel, which is examined based on 100 articles about the conflict from national

newspapers published between 7 and 14 October 2023 (period 1) and between 7 and 14 April 2024 (period 2). The articles were found through structured searches in Infomedia. Sampling: the method is based on simple random selection from the 21 national newspapers, ensuring minimal bias. The searches included the keywords "war," "Israel," and "Gaza." In the first period, the number of articles in the Infomedia search was 209, and by selecting the first 50 of these provided a more representative sample. In the second period, the number of articles was 68 and again the first 50 articles were selected. The topic, which is very topical and therefore highly publicised, was chosen due to its measurable nature.

3. Literature review

In the following chapter, I will explore the topic of *media effect*, where my primary theorist can be seen as *Denis McQuail*, and where the aim is to see how his theory can be complemented by *Fabian Thomas*' studies of media effect patterns and *Stig Hjarvad*'s medialisation theory. This chapter aims to illuminate how media effects play a role in the construction of social realities and identities, and how these processes are embedded in wider structures and power relations.

3.1 The media effect and its understanding

Denis McQuail who belongs to the older generation of media effects researchers, was a prominent media effects researcher who examined the influence of media on society and highlighted how factors such as governments and technology can influence this development. However, *Barrie Gunter* of the Independent Broadcasting Authority criticised McQuail's 1983 *Mass Communication Theory* for exhibiting a sociological bias as McQuail's theory overlooks psychological and social psychological perspectives, and Gunter believes that a broader theoretical approach would have improved its usefulness as an introduction to mass communication (Gunter, 1984). Nevertheless, I adopt McQuail's theory as the foundational framework for this thesis, as the third edition includes several revisions and additions, and because his concepts are directly applicable and align with the theories of Thomas and Hjarvad.

Media 'effects' are simply the consequences of what the mass media do, whether intended or not. The expression 'media power', on the other hand, refers to a general potential on the part of the media to have effects, especially of a planned kind (McQuail, 1994, p. 333).

The media are not just passive mediators, but active actors that shape our cultural and social landscape. This is particularly evident during adolescence, a malleable period when individuals search for role models and frames of reference to define their identity. McQuail points out that changes in societal conditions over time have affected the perception of the media's impact from powerful to limited and back to powerful.

The role of the media is amplified in times of crisis and moral panic as the public increasingly looks to the media for guidance and information, as described in the case study in Hjarvad and Kristensen's article (Hjarvad & Kristensen, 2014). The media's effect is particularly evident in relation to topics outside of the individual's direct experience, meaning that the impact is greatest on children and young people. "Media power" refers to the media's potential to influence society, while "media effectiveness" refers to the media's ability to achieve planned effects. According to McQuail, media effects can include both intended and unintended changes, minor adjustments or maintenance of existing conditions. This complexity, both cognitively and affectively, demonstrates the ability of media to shape perceptions and reinforce the status quo (McQuail, 1994, pp. 327-328; 332-335)

The older but nuanced understanding of media effects outlined by McQuail lays the foundation for how exactly these effects can be analysed and understood.

In this context, the contribution of *Fabian Thomas*, as a representative of the newer generation of researchers, becomes particularly relevant, especially through his analysis of media effect patterns using longitudinal data and statistical models. Thomas confirms McQuail's findings and thus complements our understanding of these patterns of media effects, 'transactional', 'fading', and 'longitudinal' effects, i.e. how media effects can appear briefly, gradually diminish over time, or be sustained and possibly amplified over a longer period, demonstrating how these can be identified and analysed through methodologically robust research. By utilising advanced statistical techniques to distinguish between within-person effects and between-person effects, Thomas offers a valuable tool for examining how individual and collective media effects evolve over time. Thomas' perspective is therefore central to the thesis' analysis of the media coverage of the Israel/Palestine conflict, as it explains how media exposure can have both immediate and lasting effects. By applying Thomas' theory, the thesis can examine how media effects influence public attitudes in both the short and long term. Although Gunter points out that McQuail does not sufficiently include research on how audiences actually perceive and react to media content, parts of McQuail's theories are still well-founded. As the thesis uses its own research that includes data from respondents, Thomas' theory will strengthen McQuail's perspectives. This not only highlights the importance of longitudinal studies in media research but also adds a new dimension to the discussion on the role of media effects by emphasising the need for detailed and contextualised analysis. Through his empirical approach, Thomas sheds light on the complex dynamics behind the influence of media effects on individual attitudes, behavioural patterns and social norms, enriching our understanding of the power and limits of media (Gunter, 1984) (Thomas, 2022, pp. 408-411; 419-422) (McQuail, 1994, pp. 335-338; 348-349)

3.1.1 Media influence

Thomas' article explains how the multifaceted influence of the media on our attitudes and behaviours can be seen over time, highlighting the importance of understanding these effects in order to grasp the essence of the media's wider societal power. This perspective serves as a vital link to the discussion of how the media, through agenda-setting and highlighting specific issues, exercise power by shaping public and political perceptions and priorities. By recognising the long-lasting aspect of media effects, where certain influences can intensify over time, it becomes clear that media influence extends far beyond immediate reactions and therefore plays a central role in defining societal values and behavioural norms. This perspective on the power of the media to both shape and reinforce societal trends further emphasises the need for an in-depth and critical approach to analysing and understanding the role of media in our lives.

The media has considerable power to set the agenda and influence what issues the public considers important. Through their selection and presentation of information, they can shape political discussions and influence decision-making in democratic processes. This is also emphasised by McQuail, who points out that students and campaign managers have tried to incorporate personal influence as a variable in their research and apply this to the successful management of commercial and political campaigns. Advertising plays a central role in creating a consumer culture that can have negative consequences, but media developments have also created opportunities for empowerment and social change (McQuail, 1994, pp. 327-329; 339-342; 350).

We dress for the weather as forecast, buy something because of an advertisement, go to a film mentioned in a newspaper, react in countless ways to media news, to films, to music on the radio, and so on (McQuail, 1994, p. 327).

However, media effects vary depending on an individual's background, personal experiences and media literacy, emphasising the need for media literacy. Information on critical thinking and media analysis from a young age can strengthen an individual's ability to understand and navigate the media landscape in a reflective way. Media operate within social and cultural structures that influence perceptions and behaviour (McQuail, 1994, pp. 329-330; 341).

In summary, McQuail points out the importance of recognising media influence, but also the necessity of a critical approach to avoid biased coverage. This leads naturally to Thomas' media effect pattern theory, which elaborates on how media influence can manifest as constant and persistent effects, which is central to the further analysis of media influence in this thesis.

[3.1.2 Media effect patterns](#)

Thomas' media effect pattern theory focuses on measuring patterns of media influence. In particular, the drench theory, which shows that influence is constant and does not occur in dribs and drabs or with a delayed reaction, is central to analysing how media has a lasting impact on audiences (Thomas, 2022, p. 403).

A Drench

B Drip

C Delay

→ Presence of media effect - - -> Absence of media effect

The Appearance of Media Effects

Figure 1

In this context, I shall briefly clarify the concepts presented in Figure 1 above, which illustrate the theory of effects that analyses media influences over time. Thomas' states that it is essential to distinguish between the time of onset of the effect and its duration. This includes an understanding of when media effects occur and how long they last. Different patterns such as *drench*, *drip* and *delay* illustrate the dynamics of media effects' manifestation and duration, emphasising the role of time in understanding media effects (Thomas, 2022, p. 403).

The "drench effect" can be explained as a media effect that occurs as an immediate and strong impact from specific media elements, especially when the content is distinctive, deviant or intense. This means that certain media elements can have a very powerful effect on the recipient's initial response right after exposure, typically in the very first measurements (Thomas, 2022, pp. 403-404). One way to understand the drench effect is to visualise it with symbols and timelines. Imagine that an individual i is exposed to a media element at a given time t . The drench effect can then be described with the formula:

Outcome $ti = \gamma_1 \times (\text{media item})^1$

Here, γ_1 is the strong immediate media effect that occurs right after exposure to the media item, measured by the first response Outcome ti . This effect occurs at the time of exposure and manifests as a significant initial response. Figure 1, panel A (the drench pattern) illustrates how two media elements exert a direct and strong effect γ_1 on the receiver's first response.

This differs from the other media effect patterns as in panel B, the delay effect γ_2 (delayed effect characterised by previous media elements not affecting the immediate response but manifesting in subsequent results, indicating a delayed media effect.) or as in panel C, the drip effect γ_3 (gradual accumulation of small effects that are diminishing.), as the drench effect is immediate and powerful (Thomas, 2022, pp. 403-405)

In the context of this thesis, a media element can refer to a single unit of media content, such as an article in a newspaper, as this media element is the subject of the content analysis. In other words, it refers to a concrete piece of content that the recipients are exposed to, and which can potentially have an effect when analysing media effects such as drench, drip or delay. Similarly, 'Outcome' may refer to a response or reaction from the recipient, the individual i , to the media element, where t represents the time elapsed from receiving the message to the occurrence of the reaction, thereby indicating a media effect, for example, γ_1 in the case of strong immediate effects.

As with the above example of media effects, the duration of these effects can be broken down into general patterns: 'fleeting', 'fading', and 'far-reaching' media effects. *Fleeting effects* show an immediate reaction to a media element that diminishes as attention is directed to new stimuli. This degradation pattern is seen when the most recently exposed media item dominates the media effect, described by Thomas as 'recency effects', which can be interpreted as 'novelty effects' and describes how newly received information affects recipients more than previous information by making the latest information more salient and influential, indicating that the initial effect has no lasting impact on subsequent results. (Thomas, 2022, p. 405).

Whereas McQuail focuses on the media impact perspective from a strategic point of view, emphasising that effects of online communications/campaigns can be both intended and unintended and vary between being short-term and long-term. This perspective highlights the importance of careful planning and evaluation of media campaigns, for example, to ensure that the desired effects are achieved while minimising unwanted side effects or understood as part of the overall impact of the media content (McQuail, 1994, pp. 335-338).

In the adapted figure 2 below, inspired by Thomas' original figure, which contained the description of nine media effect patterns, I have chosen to include only the in-depth explanation of the drench effect, as this is my focus (Thomas, 2022, pp. 407-408).

¹ (Thomas, 2022, p. 403)

Descriptions and Examples for Nine Media Effect Patterns

Drench	
Fleeting	Media items at t affect outcomes at t but not subsequent outcomes ($t + 1, \dots, t + n$)
	Example: In the context of narrative persuasion, scholars argued that to the extent that recipients “are absorbed into a story or transported into a narrative world, they may show effects of the story on their real-world beliefs” (Green & Brock, 2000, p. 701). The media effect of being transported itself, however, appears during exposure and is limited to the period of exposure to a specific narrative; representing an immediate effect caused by a single media item
Fading	Media items at t affect outcomes at t and subsequent outcomes ($t + 1, \dots, t + n$) while the magnitude of the effects becomes weaker as time passes

Appearance and Duration of Media Effects

L.K. Byron/ F. Thomas

Continued

Continued

Drench	
	Example: In the context of framing effects, Baden and Lecheler (2012) argued that fading effects appear “if the frame is fully familiar [...] and the relevant knowledge has a medium level of chronic accessibility” (p. 371). For example, Lecheler and de Vreese (2011) showed immediate framing effects that started to fade away after two weeks (at least for specific groups)
Far reaching	Media items at t affect outcomes at t and subsequent outcomes ($t + 1, \dots, t + n$) while the magnitude of the effects remains stable or increases as time passes
	Example: The drench hypothesis (Greenberg, 1988) claims that exposure to specific outstanding characters in TV shows immediately influence recipients’ attitudes or beliefs; these characters are the “portrayals [...] we will carry with us in memory” (Greenberg, 1988, p. 99)

L.K. Byron/ F. Thomas

Appearance and Duration of Media Effects

Figure 2

Drench effect is first seen in Figure 2 as 'fleeting', which refers media content influencing outcomes at the time of exposure but having no lasting effect. When a user is engrossed in a story/narrative, the simple media experience may subsequently affect the recipients' reality, but the effect disappears after exposure. This is followed by the fading effect, where media content affects both immediate and subsequent outcomes, but the effect diminishes over time, these are seen as media effects where the effect of a given media impact becomes weaker after a few weeks. Finally, the far-reaching effect is where media content affects both immediate and subsequent outcomes and the effect remains stable or increases over time.

To go a little deeper into the interpretation of the figure, it can be seen that time t and subsequent outcomes ($t + 1, \dots, t + n$) refer to a sequence of times and the respective outcomes. So, time t and $+1$ are the initial time at which an event or exposure takes place. Subsequent outcomes ($t + 1, \dots, t + n$) show the outcomes or effects that occur in the consecutive time points after the initial event or exposure. For example, where t is the time of exposure to a given news story, $t+1$ will be the first-time interval in which to measure the effect of that exposure, $t+2$ the next after that, and so on until $t+n$, which is the last time of measurement in a given period. This is used to examine how an initial impact develops over time (Thomas, 2022, pp. 406-410).

For example, I can take the case of the thesis and the media's dissemination of it throughout both periods as a starting point, with the date of the outbreak of the conflict as $t+1$ and until the last date in the last period as $t+n$. Subsequently, I can analyse how the individual's response has been and thus assess outcome ti . I can then test whether there is a γ_1 effect and finally assess whether this is related to the media element, i.e. whether Thomas' criteria for Outcome $ti = \gamma_1 \times (\text{media item})ti^2$ are met, and whether this is an immediate effect, i.e. a drench effect. Furthermore, I will investigate whether the effect is fleeting, fading or far reaching.

3.1.3 The nature of media effects

Together, these perspectives create a more detailed picture of the nature and dynamics of media effects. McQuail's emphasis on media effects in relation to intended and unintended consequences provides an overall framework for understanding media influence. Thomas' detailed exploration of fading and far-reaching effects adds depth to this understanding by illustrating how specific types of media content can have varying long-term impacts on individuals' attitudes and behaviour (Thomas, 2022, pp. 405-406).

I see these perspectives complementing each other by offering an integrated approach to the study of media effects, with McQuail's theoretical and planning-orientated perspective complemented by Thomas' empirical and pattern-based analysis. Together they emphasise the importance of considering both the immediate and long-term effects of media content, as well as the need for careful assessment of both desired and undesired outcomes of media communication. This unified view offers valuable insights for media studies researchers on how best to design, implement and evaluate media campaigns to achieve the most positive social and individual outcomes.

Stig Hjarvad's medialisisation theory, which is central to understanding how media shapes social and cultural frameworks in modern societies, is crucial to the thesis' analysis of media influence on cultural and social processes. Hjarvad's theory complements McQuail's media effects theory by offering a macro sociological understanding of the role of media as both creators and reflectors of societal change. In his theory of mediatisation, Hjarvad highlights that the media plays a key role in shaping the cultural and social framework within which modernisation processes take place (Hjarvad, 2009, pp. 5-7).

Hjarvad explains mediatisation as an integral part of the overall modernisation process of society and culture, making it an essential concept in modern sociology. Although the pioneers of sociology such as *Max Weber* and *Karl Marx* primarily focused on industrialisation and urbanisation without giving much importance to the media, later developments and the expansion of mass media have emphasised the need to integrate a media perspective into sociological theory. Although media studies has developed independently of sociology for periods, recent research has promoted the reunification of

² (Thomas, 2022, p. 403)

the two fields by examining the role of media in modern social processes such as globalisation and networking . The theory of mediatisation, which describes the media as both product and co-creator of modern social structures, emphasises the centrality of mediatisation in the understanding of modernity, making the theory of the impact of media on culture and society a necessity in contemporary sociological research. Media is seen to play an increasingly important and integral role in the modernisation of society and culture. This implies a development where media contributes to the transformation of social relations by moving them from existing contexts to new social contexts. Mediatisation is therefore a central part of what it means to live in a modern society, as it is both constitutive of modern social structures and of the changes in culture and society that characterise the modern. This process highlights the need for a deeper dialogue and integration between media studies and sociology to understand the societal changes that occur through and with the media (Hjarvad, 2009, pp. 32-33).

Hjarvad's view of media as both a product of and a driving force behind society's modernisation processes is thus in line with McQuail's view, as medialisation theory describes how media not only reflects society but actively helps to reshape it by embedding social relations in new contexts through their influence on communication, interaction and information flow.

Hjarvad's statements below about mediated interaction and its role in optimising social interaction for the individual actor by relieving and allowing greater control over information exchange complement McQuail and Thomas' media effects models by offering a contextualised understanding of how media affects individual behaviour and social relationships:

Another characteristic of mediated interaction is that the media allows the individual actor *optimise the social interaction for their own benefit* by both relieving the actor and allowing greater control over the exchange of information. The media *relieves* the individual relations with the outside world, as the media makes it possible to achieve greater contact with less effort (Hjarvad, 2009, p. 23).

McQuail's model is primarily concerned with the sequence of effects from cognitive learning to affective response and conative effect/behaviour, at different levels of involvement. Thomas' model deals with specific types of media effect patterns. Hjarvad's perspective extends both of these understandings by emphasising how media not only affects individuals through a linear sequence of effects, but also by changing the fundamental dynamics of social interaction. Media enables individuals to navigate social relationships with less risk/effort and increased control, which implies a more indirect form of media effect that is not only about the direct impact of content, but also about the wider social consequences of media use (McQuail, 1994, pp. 348-349) (Hjarvad, 2009, pp. 23; 30-33).

The connection between Hjarvad's assumption and McQuail's model can be seen in how media mediates social processes and influences behavioural patterns. While McQuail focuses on the individual psychological processes that lead from perception to behaviour,

Hjarvad highlights how media facilitates these processes on a social level by enabling more efficient and controlled interactions. In doing so, both theories emphasise the importance of considering media as active participants in shaping our social media landscape.

McQuail then comments on Ray's 'effect hierarchy' as a process that goes from cognitive learning (the most common effect) to the affective response (such as liking or disliking something, opinion, attitude) and ends with the 'conative' effect (behaviour/action). He explains Ray's arguments that this model is only useful under conditions of high involvement (high interest/attention). This is basically because in low involvement (which is common in many situations where we watch TV, for example, and especially when commercials are shown) the sequence can go directly from cognition to behaviour, with an affective adjustment occurring later to bring the attitude in line with the behaviour. A model of media effect is therefore proposed in which the process is initiated with low involvement and proceeds through the realisation of dissonance to learning, accumulating in the formation of considered ideas and potentially action. This process is particularly effective under conditions of repeated exposure, as seen in systematic campaigns (McQuail, 1994, p. 340).

The difference between McQuail's and Hjarvad's focus can challenge an integrated understanding of the role of media, as their analyses operate on different levels. McQuail combines micro and macro perspectives and sees the media as active actors that shape the cultural and social landscape. He emphasises their ability to influence through cognitive, affective and conative effects, showing a broad understanding of media influence from awareness to action. Hjarvad's macro-oriented approach, on the other hand, focuses on medialisatation and the integration of media into social and cultural spheres. Hjarvad examines how media transforms institutions and practices, thus contributing to the process of modernisation (McQuail, 1994, pp. 335-341) (Hjarvad, 2009, pp. 32-33).

Thomas' article, which analyses media effect patterns through longitudinal studies and statistical models, thus presents a methodological extension of the theoretical framework established by McQuail and Hjarvad. Whereas McQuail deals with the influence of media effects on levels from the individual to the societal, and Hjarvad focuses on the impact of mediatization on cultural and social institutions, Thomas offers a tool for an accurate analysis of these influences over time. Through the identification of specific patterns of impact and the separation between the different effects, Thomas demonstrates the use of statistical analyses to map and understand the dynamics of media influences. His perspectives thus serve as a link between theoretical insights and empirical research in the field of media effects, not only increasing the understanding of the complexity of media effects but also highlighting the methodological rigour of examining the unfolding of media effects over time (McQuail, 1994, pp. 335-341) (Thomas, 2022, pp. 405-406) (Hjarvad, 2009, pp. 32-33).

3.1.4 Intentionality

McQuail's definition of *intentionality* refers to conscious actions or states directed towards an object or condition in the world. In philosophy and cognitive science, it describes the way in which thoughts, feelings and actions are purposeful and meaningful. It implies that mental states always have a content to which they are directed or about something, creating a connection between the mind and the world (McQuail, 1994, pp. 336-337).

Figure 3

McQuail's Intentionality-media effects perspective, Figure 3, includes 'news learning', which is about short-term cognitive effects of media exposure, assessed through memory, recognition and understanding. Together with 'individual reaction', these concepts are used to analyse the results of the thesis. In addition, 'distribution of knowledge' is examined, which looks at the influence of media on the distribution of knowledge between social groups. "Collective reaction describes how many people simultaneously experience the same effects in a common context, which can lead to common actions such as fear, anxiety and anger that can result in panic or civil unrest, relevant to the demonstrations. Demonstrations are interpreted as 'event outcomes', analysing the role of media during large and small events (McQuail, 1994, pp. 336-338).

These changes can strengthen or weaken cultural identity, as in the example where a Jewish PhD student was met with threatening battle cries from the tent camp demonstration on South Campus, including slogans such as "no to Nakba - globalise the intifada" and "there is only one solution, intifada revolution" (Trolle, 2024).

Both the 'collective reaction' and the 'individual reaction' can be considered unplanned effects. For example, the pro-Palestinian 'sit down' demonstration at the University of Copenhagen's South Campus, where both teachers and students were harassed (Kirkebæk-Johansson & Trolle, 2024), can be seen as an example of these unplanned effects, showing how individuals and groups are affected both collectively and individually by media coverage, further illustrating how conflict manifests itself in a Danish context.

These theorists emphasise the importance of a critical approach to the media, which not only disseminates information but can also influence societal norms and values. This leads naturally to the agenda-setting theory, which explains the media's influence on what topics are prioritised by the public.

[3.2 Agenda setting](#)

Agenda-setting theory is central to the thesis' analysis as it sheds light on how media content can influence the public's perception of what issues are important. The thesis uses agenda-setting as a theoretical framework to understand how the media not only disseminates information but also shapes society's agenda by prioritising certain issues over others. The choice of this theory is motivated by its broad application in media research and its relevance for examining the relationship between media coverage of the Israel/Palestine conflict and public attitudes towards the conflict.

Agenda-setting theory assumes that there is a correlation between news media content and public opinion. Or rather, that the public's perception of what is important reflects the media's agenda (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, p. 34).

Eskjær and Helles explain agenda-setting theory as a study of the relationship between media content and public opinion, based on the hypothesis that our understanding of political and social realities is largely shaped by the media. If the hypothesis was confirmed, one could either analyse media content to predict what the public considers important or use opinion polls to conclude what is on the media agenda. However, combining content analysis with opinion polls provides different types of data, which together make it more likely that a correlation between media content and public opinion may exist (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 128-129).

Maxwell McCombs' *Setting the Agenda: The Mass Media and Public Opinion* (2004) has been met with some criticism, especially from American scholars such as Gerald M. Kosicki, who points out that McCombs' agenda-setting model faces conceptual and practical challenges in explaining modern media relations and audience behaviour (Kosicki, 2006).

However, I choose to include this older theory as it illuminates aspects relevant to the thesis and compare it to the newer generation of theory represented by Eskjær and Helles.

This role of the news media in identifying the key issues and topics of the day and their ability to influence the salience of these issues and topics on the public agenda has come to be called the agenda-setting role of the news media (McCombs, 2014, p. 1).

While Eskjær and Helles above seem somewhat reluctant to accept the theory, McCombs is different and explains that the news media's ability to identify and highlight the important issues of the day and their influence on which issues are considered important by the public is called agenda-setting, and in his opinion the theory has great validity (McCombs, 2014, p. 1).

McComb's original study conducted a quantitative content analysis of media content over three weeks, covering both national and local newspapers and TV news. The study identified the political themes that dominated the campaign coverage. At the same time, interviews were conducted in which respondents were asked which topics they found most important (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, p. 34).

The study showed a clear correlation between media content and voters' assessment of important issues, which for McCombs and Shaw was indicative of the agenda-setting function of media (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 34-35).

Although Eskjær and Helles describe how McCombs clearly has an indication to justify the theory, Eskjær and Helles explain how they interpret that McCombs only talks about assumed correlations: "agenda-setting theory assumes that a correlation exists between news media content and public opinion". However, McCombs clearly states that "agenda-setting does assign a central role to the news media in initiating items for the public agenda", and goes on to justify his position by arguing that critics of agenda-setting theory claim that both the public and the media are not influenced by, but merely react to their environment (McCombs, 2014, p. 24).

In the realm of public affairs, the greater an individual's need for orientation, the more likely he or she is to attend to the agenda of the news media with their wealth of information on politics and government (McCombs, 2014, p. 77)

McCombs explains that in public affairs, the greater a person's need for information, the more likely they are to follow the news media agenda to obtain information about politics and government. On websites and television news, repeated coverage over several days thus serves as a clear indication of a topic's importance.

Various factors such as front-page placement, headline size and article length signal the importance of news topics. The public uses these signals to prioritise topics and the media's agenda often becomes the public's agenda. The placement of a topic on the public agenda is the first step in the formation of public opinion (McCombs, 2014, pp. 1-2; 77).

Beyond attitudes and opinions, the pictures of reality created by the media have implications for personal behaviours, ranging from college applications to voting on election day (McCombs, 2014, p. 110).

McCombs highlights that the media's portrayal of reality influences personal decisions such as education choices and voting behaviour. For example, news media and consumers are particularly interested in opinion polls during political campaigns. Before analysing the distribution of attitudes, the key issues for the public must be identified. The agenda-setting role of the media determines which topics the population considers important. This influence is argued by some to be not consciously planned, but an unintended consequence of the media's selection and emphasis on certain issues, which then fits with McQuail's theory of unplanned effects. However, the elite media does play a key role in putting new topics on the agenda, while the framing of the news by key journalists is a clear example of intermedia agenda-setting. This process occurs daily when local media construct their agenda based on the material they receive, for example, from news agencies (McCombs, 2014, pp. 1-2; 100; 128-132) (McQuail, 1994, pp. 336-338).

Eskjær and Helles explain that agenda-setting studies use content analyses and opinion polls to examine how media content influence's public opinion. The correlation between these metrics supports the hypothesis of the agenda-setting role of media, which cannot be confirmed through stand-alone analyses, but requires a combination of both methods. This combination illustrates how content analysis can connect communication content with the context of the receiver through quantitative metrics. Similarly, the relationship with the sender can be explored through a combination of quantitative content analysis and qualitative research interviews (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 128-129).

As Hjarvad and Kristensen point out in their article, media often follow elite consensus in political agreement, while in disagreement they may present alternative views, but remain closely tied to elite perspectives. Through agenda-setting, it can thus be argued that media topic choices shape public priorities, which requires a combined method of media content and opinion analyses. The next section describes the quantitative and qualitative methods used in the thesis (Hjarvard & Kristensen, 2014).

4. Method description

Methodologically, the thesis utilises Explanatory Sequential design. This type of mixed methods design is often associated with triangulation, where the aim is to compare multiple sets of results (Bryman, 2016 , p. 640; 643; 649) (Bryman, 2021, pp. 557-559; 567-571). The focus is on topic choice, attitudes and views, with particular emphasis on the analysis of Danish national newspaper articles from the two selected periods. The results of the content analysis thus form the overarching theme of the thesis: the role of the media in shaping public attitudes and perceptions. Through an integrated approach consisting of quantitative content analysis, survey, subsequent qualitative interviews and an intercoder reliability test, the thesis examines how media content influences citizens. This process is continuously explained in the thesis.

4.1 Quantitative method

The quantitative method quantifies communication content such as text, audio or images by transforming elements into codes, enabling statistical calculations of frequency, representativeness and uncertainty, among other things. This form of analysis provides a systematic overview and supports the formulation of hypotheses about the context and potential effects of communication (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, p. 10).

This thesis uses quantitative methodology to analyse selected articles and subsequent surveys to create an in-depth understanding of media impact. Thus, the thesis uses statistical techniques to examine text corpora and draw conclusions about messages, context and communication processes. The thesis identifies patterns and structures in the selected sample of articles. This differs from semiotic text analysis, which focuses on individual texts and their sender-related elements (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 16-17)

The quantitative method is used in the thesis first for the content analysis, where communicative elements are quantified and coded for statistical calculations. Then, surveys are conducted depending on the research questions (see Appendix 1) and the time available. The choice and order of methods is determined by the research questions and the amount of time available to complete the survey. Different questions may require different approaches and time frames to obtain reliable results (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 11-12; 105; 132).

The quantitative methodology provides an overview of the overall themes and attitudes in the selected data set. To ensure a systematic approach, the next section describes the article selection process, including the principles of sampling and the subsequent coding of the material.

4.1.1 Sampling

The thesis uses the principles of Eskjær and Helles (2021) for sample selection, coding scheme development and data processing. They emphasise the necessity of a rigorous sampling strategy, which, in this thesis, for example, can explain the sample size, the criteria for selection, the variables used, and the period studied, as elaborated upon in the section below. Sampling refers to data selection in empirical studies.

The thesis uses sampling to determine the scope of the study, especially in media analysis, by selecting media, platforms and time periods. Census provides complete data but is often resource intensive, while sampling requires consideration of representativeness and bias .

Simple random selection ensures that all elements of a population have an equal chance of being selected (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 54-55). Probability-based selection enables generalisation through methods such as simple random and systematic selection (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 58-61; 62-64).

The thesis employs simple random sampling to select randomised articles from Danish national newspapers, which mitigates bias and ensures a representative sample of media coverage (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 54-58).

The strategy for sampling articles for the thesis means that the sample size of the content analysis is 100 articles, all articles are news articles published in Danish national newspapers in the period from 7 October to 14 October 2023 (period 1) and again in the period from 7 April to 14 April 2024 (period 2). The first period was chosen because on 7 October 2023, Hamas carried out a surprise attack against Israel in which around 1,200 Israelis were killed and approximately 240 people were abducted as hostages, which was the beginning of the conflict, and because such a conflict can be measurable due to its timeliness (Jørgensen, 2023, p. 15). The second period was chosen because I want to examine the media coverage six months after the beginning of the conflict to assess any measurable differences between the two periods (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 61-63)

The limitation to these periods is therefore chosen to ensure a representative sample of media coverage over time. This limitation has several purposes, but first and foremost, this analysis of media coverage in two separate periods allows us to identify changes and patterns in reporting. Only national newspapers are included to ensure consistency and relevance in coverage. The different search options Infomedia offers are categorised as either "period", "media", or "plus search options". I first select the periods, then media that allow for specific search criteria, such as "all media", "national dailies (21)", "regional and local dailies (87)", "local weeklies (475)", "magazines (658)", "news agencies (14)", "web sources (1270)", TV features (48)", "radio features (145)" and "other (37)". If I had chosen to search only for the word "war" and selected all years and all media, the result would be 1,870,862 articles.

Such a total count would be resource-intensive and therefore unrealistic for this thesis. By limiting the searches to national daily newspapers, and the selected periods and keywords,

this sample selection ensures the analysis remains focused on the chosen topic. The media that were thus represented in the Infomedia search are shown in Figure 4-5 below, representing the two periods, where it can be seen that it is largely the same media that are represented in both periods (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 42-43; 50; 53-54; 63-65).

Representation of National Media

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Århus Stift Tidende	1	2.0	2.0	2.0
	Århus Stifttidende	2	4.0	4.0	6.0
	Avisen Danmark	4	8.0	8.0	14.0
	Berlingske Tidende	8	16.0	16.0	30.0
	Berlingste Tidende	1	2.0	2.0	32.0
	Børsen	5	10.0	10.0	42.0
	Danmark Fyns Amts Avis	1	2.0	2.0	44.0
	Ekstra Bladet	3	6.0	6.0	50.0
	Frederiksborg Amts Avis	1	2.0	2.0	52.0
	Informationen	7	14.0	14.0	66.0
	Jyllands Posten	4	8.0	8.0	74.0
	Jyllands-Posten	5	10.0	10.0	84.0
	Kristligt Dagblad	2	4.0	4.0	88.0
	MidtJyllands Avis	1	2.0	2.0	90.0
	Politiken	2	4.0	4.0	94.0
	Politiken Debat	1	2.0	2.0	96.0
	Politikken	1	2.0	2.0	98.0
	Ritzau	1	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Period 1

Figure 4

Representation of National Media

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Berlingske Tidende	1	2.0	2.0	2.0
	Avisen Danmark	6	12.0	12.0	14.0
	Berlingske Tidende	7	14.0	14.0	28.0
	Berlingske-Tidende	1	2.0	2.0	30.0
	Børsen	1	2.0	2.0	32.0
	Danmark Fyns Amts Avis	1	2.0	2.0	34.0
	Danmark Fyns AmtsAvis	1	2.0	2.0	36.0
	Ekstra Bladet	2	4.0	4.0	40.0
	Informationen	9	18.0	18.0	58.0
	Jyllands-Posten	1	2.0	2.0	60.0
	Jyllands-Posten	4	8.0	8.0	68.0
	Jyllands-POsten	1	2.0	2.0	70.0
	Kristligt Dagblad	3	6.0	6.0	76.0
	Politiken	10	20.0	20.0	96.0
	Politikken	1	2.0	2.0	98.0
	Weekendavisen	1	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Period 2

Figure 5

All articles were thus localised using the structured search in the Infomedia media database. The Infomedia searches are therefore limited to the keywords "war," "Israel," and "Gaza," the rationale for the choice of search criteria is again based on the fact that a search using the word "war" alone results in 518 articles found in national dailies alone, compared to 5,173 articles when the search is expanded to include all media within the same period. Separate searches are conducted for the two periods, the first search for period 1 with the three selected keywords contained 209 articles and the second search in period 2 with 68 articles. 50 articles out of 209 articles can be seen as more representative than if the number of articles had been larger. The first 50 articles from each search are selected, with the exception of repeated transcripts from, for example, Reuters, where only the first article is included, and subsequent repetitions are omitted (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 91-94).

4.1.2 Coding

The quantitative content analysis of the thesis is based on two key elements: the coding scheme and the coding manual. The coding scheme defines the coding categories included in the analysis, while the coding manual instructs the coding of these coding categories and variables. Coding classifies content elements based on predefined variables to quantify their occurrence, ensuring a rule-based and objective methodology that is essential for the reliability of data capture.

As the analysis in Hjarvad and Kristensen's article shows, the thesis also uses a coding manual that defines the criteria for categorising a news story as positive, negative or

neutral. Effective coding requires that the coding scheme and coding manual are developed in interaction with each other to ensure consistency (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 67-68; 70; 71-72) (Hjarvard & Kristensen, 2014).

The thesis uses a single coder, and the coding manual based on Eskjær & Helle's table 6.1 (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 69-70), provides guidelines for the coding categories used (see Appendix 2). The criteria outlined in the thesis coding manual for the coding categories used in the analysis of the articles are reflected in labels 1-3 in Figures 6-8 of the article analysis coding variables. The wording of these three labels was selected to ensure simplicity and clarity for the respondents.

By using clear and concise questions, such as "How would you describe the topic of the article?" and "Is Israel to blame for the war?" makes it easier for respondents to quickly make up their minds on complex topics. This increases both data quality and respondent engagement. Label 1 relates to the question "How would you describe the article's position?". Again, the wording of the answer options is chosen to ensure simplicity and clarity for the respondents, who can then quickly take a position on complex topics with the following closed-ended, i.e. predetermined, answer options: "Pro Israel", "Pro Palestine", "Pro Hamas", "Neutral", meaning that these are nominal scale variables. Nominal scales are used to categorise data without any ranking or numerical value between categories. In this case, each response option represents a category where none of the categories have an order or degree of value relative to the others. Label 2 relates to the question "How would you describe the topic of the article?" with the response options: War in Israel, War in Palestine, Against war, which must also be seen as nominal scale variables. Label 3 includes the question "Is Israel to blame for the war?" with the response options: Yes, Neutral, No, which can be seen as ordinal scale variables. Unlike nominal scales, where there is no ranking between categories, ordinal scales have a mutual order, but lack precise intervals between categories, making them suitable for this type of question. This methodology is rule-based and objective, which is essential to ensure the reliability of data entry (Bryman, 2016 , pp. 260; 247-249) (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 67-70; 71-72; 113-114).

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

The coding and coding categories in the thesis survey can be illustrated through the coding scheme, as shown in the screenshot of the SPSS variable view below (Figures 6-8). This electronic spreadsheet organises the variables to be coded and their respective values. The x-axis lists variables, while the individual data units are recorded on the y-axis.

The coding of the articles into the categories: "Pro Israel", "Pro Palestine", "Pro Hamas", "Neutral", is based on the criteria defined in the coding manual (see Appendix 2). To illustrate this process, I will discuss three articles out of the 100 selected from Infomedia that represent different angles of media coverage of the conflict.

First, I look at the Jyllands-Posten article from 8 October 2023, where Israel is mentioned 50 times, Hamas 25 times, Palestine 13 times, and Gaza 11 times (Jyllands-Posten, 2023). The article uses a framing that clearly positions Israel as the victim, with quotes like "surprise attack that shocked Israel" and descriptions of "militiamen pulling an Israeli soldier alive from burning tanks". These word choices create sympathy for Israel, and Israel is portrayed as the aggrieved party. Conversely, Hamas is portrayed as the aggressor with phrases such as "The heavy rain of rockets from Gaza, which Hamas has named 'Operation Al-Aqsa

Flood'" (Jyllands-Posten, 2023). I justify the coding of this article as Pro-Israel by its unambiguous portrayal of Israel as the victim in the conflict.

Next, I analyse Ekstra Bladet's article from 10 October 2023 (Ekstra-Bladet, 2023), which mentions Israel 28 times, Hamas 14 times, Palestine 5 times and Gaza 10 times. The article focuses on how Hamas plans to kill Israeli hostages, as evidenced by quotes such as "The Islamist movement Hamas will start killing Israeli hostages" (Ekstra-Bladet, 2023). Israel is described as a nation under attack and the reader is presented with a context in which Israel's response is justified. This describes Hamas as the aggressor and Israel as the victim, making it clear why the article is coded as Pro-Israel.

For comparison, I look at Politiken's article from 13 October 2023 (Politiken, 2023), which portrays a different type of angle. The article mentions Israel 13 times, Hamas 2 times, Palestine 3 times and Gaza 8 times, but here the emphasis is not on the conflict but on the spread of *fake news* via social media. Although the article describes atrocities committed by Hamas against Israeli civilians, the primary focus is on the spread of misinformation. This shift in focus away from the conflict and towards social media explains why the article is coded as Neutral, as it does not directly address the conflict, but instead discusses a broader issue (Politiken, 2023).

By comparing the three articles, it becomes clear how differences in framing and focus affect the coding used. Jyllands-Posten and Ekstra Bladet both have a clear pro-Israel slant, which can be seen in their descriptions of Israel as the victim and Hamas as the aggressor. Politiken, on the other hand, takes a more neutral approach, viewing the conflict through a technological lens. This difference can be explained through *framing theory*, where the media's choice of angle and word choice creates a certain understanding of the conflict for readers (McCombs, 2014, pp. 101-104) (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 74-76).

This rigorous approach is applied to all articles to ensure consistent and objective coding (Bryman, 2016, pp. 260; 247-249) (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 67-70; 71-72; 113-114).

In order to operationalise these differences in framing and examine their correlation with attitudinal shifts in the recipients, the thesis uses tools such as SPSS software designed to make the coding process easy and efficient. SPSS is elaborated in section 3.1.5. The thesis coding scheme thus contains sufficient metadata to ensure clarity and organisation of data. The metadata includes project title, data sources, registration times, names, etc. which is important to maintain an overview and coherence in the coding work, especially in digital data management. As shown in the survey coding scheme's "Variable View," the variables listed under the columns "Name" and "Label" include, for example, the variable for "How do you see the situation as of May 2024?" (Figure 9) (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 71-72; 112-114).

Figure 9

The coding categories in the survey are structured into 10 questions (see Appendix 4), each with carefully selected answer options that are predefined and limited to between three and five options. In addition to the response option categories, ratio scale variables are also used here, as I also ask about age. Unlike ordinal and nominal scales, which only allow for ranking and categorisation, a ratio scale allows for both comparisons and meaningful calculations, such as averages, differences, and ratios. This structure is deliberately chosen to ensure that the analysis remains rigorous and focussed on the key areas of analysis, while keeping the subsequent survey analysis precise and targeted. Furthermore, the limitation in the number of response options is designed to minimise the time burden on respondents, which is particularly important when dealing with topics that may be perceived as sensitive. In such cases, the questions can be perceived as threatening, which can lead to respondents feeling judged by their answers. To reduce this risk and encourage more open and willing participation, it is important that respondents are not forced to elaborate on their answers or respond to an open-ended question, but instead can choose between the predetermined, closed-ended response options. This creates a safer environment for participation and reduces the potential resistance that can arise when dealing with sensitive topics, which in turn contributes to a higher quality and reliability of the data collected (Bryman, 2016, pp. 260; 247-249;) (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 71-72; 103; 112-114).

4.1.3 Coder consensus and intercoder reliability

Qualifications of the coder are essential to ensure reliability in the content analyses of the thesis. The coder must have an in-depth knowledge of the language and culture surrounding the subject under investigation, whether it be media, film or otherwise. If coders lack this

knowledge, a thorough training process may be necessary to familiarise them with both the object of study and coding principles.

There is often a risk of *coder consensus*, where coders who develop the coding scheme and coding manual can achieve a uniform understanding of the coding categories and process, which can lead to biased data. This can create an implicit bias in data entry and compromise the replicability of the study. One method to counteract this is the use of pilot testing and joint coding to ensure objectivity and reduce personal interpretation in coding (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 76-77).

As the thesis has only one coder, it is crucial to ensure consistency and reliability in the coding process. *Intercoder reliability* refers to the degree of agreement between coders when they classify the same communication content based on the same coding categories. It measures how consistent and reliable the coding is by assessing whether different coders, in this thesis the coder and the test subjects participating in the subsequent test, arrive at the same results. Thus, the thesis implements an *intercoder reliability test* by repeated coding, based on the same coding scheme and coding manual, conducted through this external review. Therefore, intercoder reliability is relevant to the thesis, as it helps to ensure both consistency and accuracy in coding.

A simple measure to avoid code consensus is to (once again) use a pilot test. In this case carried out by one or more outsiders, who can test whether the coding can actually be carried out satisfactorily based on the code scheme and code manual (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, p. 77).

The pilot test is designed to test the functionality of the research instrument and participants' understanding of the questions, while the intercoder reliability test focuses on consistency and reliability in the classification of data (coding) among coders (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 76-82).

Although this thesis has only one coder, it is still crucial to ensure consistency and reliability in the coding process. This issue is typically addressed in relation to the concept of *intercoder reliability*, which refers to the degree of agreement between coders when they classify the same communication content based on the same coding categories. Thus, when examining intercoder reliability, they test how consistent and reliable the coding is by assessing whether different coders arrive at the same results.

Since, as mentioned, only one coder appears in this thesis, an intercoder reliability test is performed by involving an external test person to code a representative selection of the material, based on the same code-schedule and code-manual (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 76-82).

[4.1.4 The intercoder reliability test](#)

The intercoder reliability test, as mentioned, measures the degree of agreement between different coders to ensure that the data entry is clear and unambiguous. A common way to test this is by overlapping coding, where multiple coders code the same elements, and their

agreement is assessed. An acceptable level of intercoder reliability is typically 85% agreement. Therefore, in single coder studies, it is important to also ensure consistency by involving a second person to do an overlap coding early in the process. This helps identify any idiosyncratic coding patterns and improves data quality (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 77-82).

However, the issue of intercoder reliability also applies to studies that utilise a single coder. The advantage of these studies is that they are usually consistently coded. The disadvantage is the risk of idiosyncrasy, where the coder develops their own personal categorisation (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, p. 78).

This illustrates the effectiveness of the coding system and shows that the methodological approach has ensured consistent patterns in the data without subjective bias. With one coder, it is essential that the coding categories are clear and consistent. The coincidence between the survey questions and the intercoder reliability test strengthens the comparability of the data. The minimal difference between the test results and the overall survey data suggests that the observed phenomena in the media content reflect a real effect rather than chance or coding bias (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 77-82) (Bryman, 2016 , pp. 260-262)(see Appendix 5a-d).

Opinions:

Opinions:

Article:	Response:			
Place X	Pro Isr	Pro Pal	Pro Ha	Neutral
1: Shock Attack from Gaza				
2: Israel Declares War				
3: Militant Palestinians Penetrate into Israel				
4: Israel Fears the Neighbor				
5: Hell Awaits in Gaza				
6: 5000 Rockets Over Israel				
7: Iran is the Joker of the War				
8: Israel Aims to Crush Hamas				
9: Hamas Has Built Tunnels in Gaza				
10: Islamic Rulers in Gaza				
11: The War in Gaza Escalates				
12: Israel Was Struck at the Heart				
13: The Enemy Will Pay				
14: Social Media Spreads Lies About Gaza				
15: Israel Intensifies Pressure				
16: Europe Tries to Find Its Footing				

Figure 10

In connection with the content analysis of the thesis, an intercoder reliability test was conducted. As the study includes an analysis of 100 articles, Eskjær and Helles recommend including a reasonable number of these articles in the test to ensure reliability, they recommend using at least 30% of the total articles, which in this case would be 30 articles, so to be on the safe side I select 32 articles. This ensures that the test is representative and provides a more reliable assessment of code agreement and data quality. The reference to a specific number is important to create a balanced assessment without overloading the process, but at the same time achieving a meaningful assessment of code consistency (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 77-80) (Bryman, 2016, pp. 260-261).

4.1.5 Result of the intercoder reliability test

To ensure that the classification of articles in the content analysis was not affected by bias, a questionnaire was used in the intercoder reliability test, as shown in Figure 10 above. In this questionnaire, the Danish word "Holdninger" is translated as "Opinions," and the same categories and variables that were previously used to code the articles were employed. The test subjects "Lasse" and "Kristian" received their own printouts of the selected articles, which they coded in accordance with the established categories. This ensured a control of

the coding process. When the results from the full survey are compared with the data from the intercoder reliability test, it is found that the differences in the distribution of answers between the two test persons only vary by a few percentages. This indicates a high degree of consistency between the two individual interpretations in the intercoder reliability test. Further analysis shows that when this data is compared to the overall result from the larger study, the test effectively supports the main result, as the agreement between the responses obtained is above 85%, indicating that the results from the study are confirmed by the intercoder reliability test. Subsequently, a pilot test of the survey was conducted to ensure its usability and comprehensibility (see Appendix 5e).

4.1.6 SPSS

This chapter aims to provide a familiarity with some basic aspects of SPSS for Windows, which is possibly the most widely used computer software for the analysis of quantitative data for social scientists (Bryman, 2016 , p. 353).

The thesis' use of SPSS offers an intuitive interface that facilitates the import and manipulation of data, making it possible to perform both simple descriptive statistics and complex multivariate analyses such as regression analysis and analysis of variance. The software's ability to handle large amounts of data makes it a valuable tool for data processing and analysis, where it is often used to generate insights and support research results (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 90-96) (Bryman, 2016 , pp. 354-356).

Figure 11

The thesis questionnaire survey was created in Google Docs and the results were transferred via the Excel sheet to SPSS. Figure 11 above exemplifies SPSS' ability to process large amounts of data and produce detailed reports and visualisations of the data transferred from Excel. Among other things, the thesis uses the SPSS "Crosstabs" function to produce schematic statistics and the "Frequencies" function to produce tables and charts that provide an immediate and clear visual overview of the desired data sets (Helles and Eskjær Page 90-96) (Bryman, 2016 , pp. 360-361).

4.1.7 Survey/questionnaire survey

The survey is based on the same sample used in the content analysis of the newspaper articles. The analysis of quantitative survey data is often an exploratory approach and therefore provides an opportunity to develop assumptions and confirm any findings from the content analysis. The purpose of the survey is to complement the existing content analysis with an additional quantitative approach that again focuses on key areas, such as topic, attitudes and views. Furthermore, the survey seeks to assess the impact of media content on the population (Bryman, 2021, p. 569).

In addition, the choice of quantitative methods, such as surveys, is essential for generalising the results to a wider population. Quantitative methods allow the collection of data from a large number of respondents, which increases the statistical power of the study. In this study, the survey is designed with closed-ended questions to ensure a high response rate and to minimise respondents' response time. This is especially important in a digital context, where participants can be prone to losing interest quickly. Likewise, care was taken not to mix categories and to ensure that good formatting was present, as this is crucial to improve the readability and comprehension of the survey. It ensures that the information is organised, easy to navigate and highlights the most important points, which is particularly important in academic and professional contexts (Bryman, 2016 , p. 227; 249; 258) (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 46-48).

Unlike the original content analysis of the 100 articles, this survey includes a specific assessment of four selected headlines from the original articles. Two of these headlines should confirm one side of the topic covered, and again two headlines highlighting the other side, thus reflecting the average opinion described in the articles from both Period 1 and Period 2 (see Appendix 7). This method, using the same sample, is designed to highlight and confirm the results of the prior content analysis, which can contribute to a deeper understanding of the study results (Bryman, 2021, pp. 371-373).

The survey was developed using Google Docs (see Appendix 4) and contained ten simple questions related to the topic. Each question was closed-ended and had between three and five pre-formulated response options, allowing respondents to choose one of the predefined answers (see Appendix 4). This structure was chosen to avoid a lengthy process where respondents had to formulate open-ended answers themselves. Such an approach would also have complicated the transfer of data from Docs via Excel to the SPSS form,

which was necessary to generate the necessary tables and statistical analyses (Bryman, 2016 , pp. 200; 247-249) (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 67-68).

One of the challenges the study faced was the distribution of the survey via social media platforms. While social media can be effective in reaching a wide audience, it is also characterised by its own rules and guidelines that can limit the distribution of research materials (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 63-65).

The survey was first published on 12 May. However, at this time I had not considered that Google Docs required respondents to enter their email addresses in order to log in and participate in the survey. This verification process deterred many potential participants from participating . One respondent contacted me and expressed a willingness to participate, but on the condition that the survey was anonymous. Based on this feedback, I then anonymised the survey and shared it in various Facebook forums, including some of the University of Copenhagen sites, sports associations and other public groups, such as "Politik i Allerød" etc. Common to groups such as "Politik i Allerød" is that they typically have over 1,000 members, which makes the groups attractive as there is an increased possibility of finding respondents in larger groups.

Unfortunately, before I found the groups mentioned above, my post was removed from other groups. For example, it was removed from the groups "Ganløse" and "Tisvildeleje hele året rundt" on the grounds that they did not permit advertisements related to sales (see Appendix 9). This was despite the fact that the group allowed posts about the sale of goods from other members' own shops in Tisvildeleje.

Other groups, such as "Ølstykke Stenløse", clearly stated on their Facebook page that they did not want the posting of surveys (see Appendix 10). On 14 May, I published the anonymised survey, with a re-posting on 20 May, where I received a total of 130 responses in the period from 14 May to 31 May (see Appendix 11).

One of the key ethical aspects of this study is the anonymisation of respondents' data. Anonymisation is essential to ensure the privacy of participants and to comply with ethical guidelines for research practices. Initially, Google Docs required respondents to enter their email addresses, which deterred many from participating. After this challenge was identified, the survey was changed to be fully anonymous. This shift was necessary to comply with ethical standards and to ensure a higher participation rate (Bryman, 2016 , pp. 125-129).

4.1.8 Other methodological considerations

A key methodological consideration in this study is the choice of structured searches in the Infomedia database. Structured searches enable a systematic and reproducible approach to data collection, which is essential to ensure the validity and reliability of the study. By choosing specific search parameters and time periods, it is possible to control for variables that may influence the results, such as seasonal news trends or sudden societal events. This

methodological rigour helps create a solid foundation for the study's conclusions (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 59-61).

The data collected in the survey will also be analysed using the statistical tools in SPSS. The focus will be on identifying patterns and correlations between media content and citizens' attitudes. The results will not only contribute to a better understanding of the impact of media content but also inform future media analyses and policy discussions. The combined approach of both content analysis and quantitative survey provides a robust methodological framework that can be used in future studies (Bryman, 2016 , p. 330).

Figure 12

Figure 12 presents both the codebook and frequencies functions in the Danish version, which are useful for generating an overview of each variable in the dataset. These functions provide information about the variable type as well as the distribution of values. This contributes to an in-depth understanding of the structure and quality of the dataset, which is essential to ensure the validity of the analytical results (Bryman, 2016 , pp. 360-361). In Figure 11, it is clearly illustrated that the nominal values include categories such as names, attitudes and topics, while the ordinal values are represented by simple answer options, such as "yes" and "no". Scaled values represent numerical data, such as dates.

For more in-depth analyses, SPSS offers the "Explore" function, which is ideal for detailed exploration of some numeric' data, however, "string" variables are not possible to use in the "dependent list" in the Explore function. As most of the datasets in the thesis survey are "string" variables, the "Frequencies" and "Crosstabs" functions are the preferred functions. These functions provide both graphical presentations and descriptive statistics, which is useful for the thesis variables. When using SPSS, it is also important to note the programme's capacity to handle missing values. The user has several strategies available to tackle this issue, including the exclusion of incomplete cases or imputation, where missing values are estimated based on available data. These methods help maintain the integrity of the analysis without distorting the statistical results. Overall, SPSS is an essential tool for researchers who want to perform thorough statistical analysis. Its flexibility and in-depth functionality allows users to customise the analysis to specific research needs, thus ensuring that both the data management and analysis phases are robust and reliable (Helles and Eskjær Page 90-96) (Bryman, 2016 , pp. 362-363).

4.2 Qualitative method

In the following, the use of the qualitative interview as a method is presented and justified. This method was chosen to enable a systematic examination of selected articles and identify trends in media coverage of the Israel-Palestine conflict. By quantifying the media content, an understanding of how specific topics are prioritised and influence public perception of the conflict is created. The thesis' quantitative content analysis is combined with qualitative content analysis and methods for a nuanced understanding of the media's impact on public opinion. The integration of quantitative and qualitative methods provides a flexible approach that illuminates both the breadth and depth of media influence. The combination of different data types enriches the analysis and provides insight into complex communication phenomena. Content analysis, which combines quantitative and qualitative techniques, is a recognised method in media and communication studies (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 123-132)

The quantitative part of the thesis focuses on counting frequencies and identifying patterns in the data, while the qualitative part examines how themes and concepts are presented and what underlying values and ideologies the texts contain. The integration of the two methods provides a deeper understanding of the construction of media content and its social and political effects. To strengthen validity and nuance the understanding of media impact, the thesis combines quantitative and qualitative methods in a mixed methods approach. This methodological integration supports triangulation, which allows for cross-checking results from different perspectives. The next section elaborates on how triangulation is used to compare the quantitative and qualitative findings, thus contributing to a more holistic analysis of media effects.

4.2.1 Mixed method and triangulation

The term mixed methods research is used as a simple shorthand to stand for research that combines quantitative and qualitative research within a single project (Bryman, 2016 , p. 635).

Furthermore, the thesis utilises mixed-methods. The term mixed methods research is a shorthand term for research that integrates both quantitative and qualitative methods in a single project. Of course, there is research that combines, for example, structured interviews with structured observation or ethnography with semi-structured interviews, but these cases represent combinations within a single research strategy. When I talk about mixed methods research, I refer to research that combines methods from both research strategies. It is noteworthy that mixed methods research has become an expanding field within the research world (Bryman, 2016 , p. 636).

However, both Eskjær & Helles and Kvale & Brinkmann state that it can be seen as problematic to mix quantitative and qualitative methods, and they justify this by stating that there are epistemological implications of combining quantitative and qualitative methods,

and that the different paradigmatic assumptions are seen by some as contradictory (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 125-126) (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015, pp. 170-171).

Bryman describes it this way in the book *Social Research Methods* from 2016:

The problem with the paradigm argument is that it rests, as does the embedded methods one, on contentions about the interconnectedness of method and epistemology in particular that cannot-in the case of social research-be demonstrated (Bryman, 2016 , p. 636)

In contrast, the view is less sanguine in Bryman's 2021 edition, where he notes that the connection between research strategy and epistemological and ontological commitments is not deterministic - that is, one does not necessarily determine the other. There is a tendency for quantitative and qualitative research to be linked to the epistemological and ontological positions, but these links are not complete. Bryman follows this up by explaining that with the growing interest in mixed methods research, various typologies have emerged that researchers have developed to identify common types of mixed methods designs. It is important to understand these typologies as they help to reflect on and engage with existing research. Furthermore, there is a growing expectation that researchers using mixed methods in their reporting will explain what type of design they have used (Bryman, 2021, pp. 565-567).

The mixed methods design used in this thesis is *The Explanatory Sequential design*, which involves first collecting and analysing quantitative data and then collecting and analysing qualitative data to elaborate or explain the quantitative results as the figure below shows (Bryman, 2021, pp. 568-569).

The Explanatory Sequential Design

(Bryman, 2021, p. 568)

The rationale for choosing this design is that you can use this approach when you believe that the overall patterns uncovered through quantitative research require an explanation that the quantitative data alone cannot provide, or when you need further insight into the quantitative results. Although the quantitative part comes first in the sequence, it does not necessarily take precedence in this design, as the explanation or elaboration provided by the qualitative findings may be particularly meaningful to the research question of the study. This type of design is often associated with *triangulation*, which aims to compare multiple sets of results. It is also used in situations where, for example, you want to balance the weaknesses of both quantitative and qualitative research by utilising the strengths of both approaches. In this way, triangulation refers to the fact that quantitative and qualitative research can be combined to mutually confirm results. In this thesis triangulation is also used, first the quantitative data is collected and analysed, such as the analysis of the articles, then surveys are conducted to identify patterns and trends. Next, qualitative data is collected and analysed, as seen in the thesis interviews, to elaborate and

explain the quantitative findings. By comparing the results from these methods, I can verify and strengthen the validity of the study's conclusions through the comparison of different data sources. By cross-checking results from different approaches, I can confirm the findings and minimise the risk of bias and error (Bryman, 2021, pp. 559-560; 569-571).

4.2.2 Interview guide

In connection with the thesis and the previous content analysis and survey, it was useful to prepare a thematization, i.e. the development of research questions and the theoretical understanding of the analysed topic. The interview survey examines for the presence of a possible media effect, already collected empirical data and the existing knowledge from the selected articles. The question guide is thus primarily designed based on previously identified themes from the content analysis and questionnaire survey. The themes will be described in detail in the results section of the thesis but are tentatively introduced in relation to an elaboration of and in the context of the interview guide (Bryman, 2016, pp. 469-471) (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015, pp. 157-158). The following conditional conditions were established as a basis for the interview study:

The research objective is to generate knowledge about the media effect on the population. At the same time, it was essential to understand the effect the media has on the individual. The content analysis focused on the sender of content and revealed significant trends in the media's approach to the topic. The analysis also showed that in the first period, attitudes were described that diametrically changed towards the second period (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015, pp. 157-158).

The survey is based on the respondents' opinions on the topic and was anonymised due to the low interest in the project, as the survey had not been anonymised. The interview study is based on the respondents from the survey who volunteered their help. The respondents had knowledge of the conflict and the media coverage of the conflict over both periods.

The purpose of the interviews was to expand knowledge in the field by gaining access to the informants' opinions. The interview study was thus intended to uncover attitudes towards a certain topic in relation to two different periods. With these premises in mind, I will look at what the theory supports:

With the many different types of interviews and interviewees described in this chapter, it is understandable that there are no general standard procedures and rules for research interviews. Furthermore, the different types of interviews are related to different types of knowledge (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015, p. 204).

Kvale and Brinkmann describe seven different types of interviews that have a relatively fixed framework for what the different categories contain. For example, the conceptual interview is described as exploring how a person or group understands and relates to specific concepts such as 'justice' or 'responsibility', and the factual interview is described as being about accurate and reliable information about specific issues with a focus on validity.

Although Kvale and Brinkmann's different interview forms are not necessarily mutually exclusive and a combination of these forms could possibly be obvious for a study on the effect of the media on respondents (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015, pp. 204-208), I choose to take a closer look at Bryman's presentations.

Bryman describes that the qualitative interview includes both semi-structured and unstructured interview types. Bryman describes 12 interview types, where the categories are described more fluidly than in Kvale and Brinkmann (Bryman, 2016, p. 201).

Semi-structured interview... typically refers to a context in which the interviewer has a series of questions that are in the general form of an interview guide but is able to vary the sequence of questions. The questions are frequently somewhat more general in their frame of reference than the questions typically found in a structured interview schedule. Also, the interviewer usually has some latitude to ask further questions in response to what are seen as significant replies (Bryman, 2016, p. 201).

Bryman explains the difference between the structured quantitative interview and the semi-structured qualitative interview as typically being less structured, as qualitative interviews focus on the participants' perspectives rather than a fixed structure to ensure measurement of key concepts, as is the case in quantitative research. Thus, it can be seen that the thesis uses the semi-structured interview form. In qualitative interviews, the research questions are more open-ended, and more emphasis is placed on understanding the interviewee's views, as opposed to quantitative interviews that reflect the researcher's predetermined interests. As I described the questions in both the content analysis and the survey, it fits well with the fixed structure and closed-ended questions, whereas the interview survey questions are open-ended, and I also asked for vague answers or got the respondent to make their point when they were missing. The interviews were conducted as one-on-one interviews so that the respondent could open up and not be coloured by the opinions or wording of others (Bryman, 2016, pp. 200; 247-249) (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, pp. 67-68).

In the research literature, there is a general lack of specific examples of how best to structure the composition and order of questions and themes in an interview guide, although Bryman provides some suggestions and a description of different points to include. Guidelines for an optimal interview process can be met to some extent by building an open and flexible structure that allows for in-depth exploration of the topics.

The final interview guide begins with an informal conversation, allowing the respondent to familiarise themselves with the interviewer and feel at ease. For instance, in one of the interviews, I ask, "how the journey there had been" and then, "if the respondent had come straight from work"—everyday topics intended to encourage the respondent to reflect on familiar situations rather than the interview itself.

This technique, which is also used in casting, aims to get the person to relax and be present in the moment. When I notice that the respondent is relaxed and more present, I ask if they are ready, after which I start recording and begin the interview. The questions are based on the previous survey questions and move from simpler questions to more complex and structured ones (see Appendix 4). The interview will be recorded and subsequently

transcribed (Bryman, 2016 , pp. 201; 409; 469-471; 479) (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015, pp. 45-47).

Although, as mentioned, the research literature does not specify the optimal structure for an interview guide, an open and flexible approach ensures a natural conversation and in-depth exploration of relevant topics. The thesis guide is designed to gradually lead from an initial, general conversation to more complex questions. With the completion of the interview guide, the thesis moves to the analysis section where the collected data is systematically examined to assess the initial hypotheses and theoretical framework.

5. Analyse

The thesis analyses how media content influences the public's perception of the importance of issues, thus contributing to the understanding of the agenda-setting role of the media and its influence on public discourse. In the following, the quantitative content analysis is presented, where the form, content and slant of media coverage is analysed using collected data with a focus on identifying statistical relationships between the variables. The thesis simply measures the shift observed in media coverage without politicising or addressing the underlying causes.

5.1 Quantitative content analysis

During the quantitative content analysis, the individual articles were classified according to the dimensions defined in the coding manual, and the results were continuously entered into the statistical programme SPSS. After this, a series of univariate analyses provided a statistical overview of the trends in the material, although these analyses alone could not determine the presence of correlations between the different variables. The analysis then entered an exploratory phase, where it became possible to test initial hypotheses regarding aspects such as form, content, angles and use of sources. This phase often involved the application of more complex statistical methods and the adaptation of the data, for example by creating new derived categories based on the original data.

These adjustments resulted in a number of variables being recoded to make the categories more operational and to better identify relationships that were not immediately apparent with the original variables. For example, the number of dimensions under the variable "attitudes" was reduced from ten to six by merging dimensions. The attitude variable, which recorded the topic of the articles, went from being nominal to being ordinal, being recoded into the categories yes, no and neutral.

There are many statistical tools for investigating relationships between two or more variables, one of which can be seen as the statistical test: they often provide an unambiguous answer - yes or no - to clearly formulated research questions, for example with label 3, identifying the attitude towards the topic described in the articles, posed through the question: "Is Israel self-inflicted in the war?". Statistical tests can therefore be seen as answers to explicit research questions. Structuring your argumentation around clearly defined questions, which can then be tested and answered definitively, often contributes positively to the organisation of both the research process and the written presentation.

5.1.1 Results from the content analysis

How has the media landscape changed within these periods? When the results for the two periods of the content analysis are considered, the following can be observed from the first period, illustrated by the barchart below, where the vertical x-axis shows the number of articles and the horizontal y-axis shows the result of the interpretation based on the instructions set out in the code manual of the attitude and angle of the articles in relation to the point "Is Israel to blame for the war" (see Figure 13).

Figure 13

In the following review of the same survey from the second period, a table is presented, illustrated by the barchart below (see Figure 14)

Figure 14

In period 1, a cumulative percentage of 96% is observed for "no" (see figure 13), while in period 2 this percentage changes to 64% for "yes" (see figure 14). In the same period, "no" decreases to 12%, and in addition, it is recorded that where in period 1 there were no neutral answers, in the 2nd period these represent 24% (see Appendix 12a-b).

In the above charts produced using the codebook function, there is a significant change in the cumulative percentages between the two measurement periods, indicating a significant shift in attitudes. From an almost unanimous endorsement of "no" in the first period to a more heterogeneous distribution of responses in the second period, with the majority answering "yes". This may indicate significant changes either in relation to the topic under investigation, the journalist's personal experiences, political influence or their perceptions of the topic.

Furthermore, the inclusion of a significant proportion of neutral responses in the second period (24%), which were not present in the first period, possibly due to the increased complexity of the topic's complexity, illustrates this.

This is often the case when investigating political colouring (bias) in news media. A common technique is to code news stories according to whether they are neutral or positive/negative in relation to a given topic, person or event (Eskjær & Helles, 2021, p. 75).

As explained in Section 2.2.2 of this thesis, this bias has been accounted for by coding with variables that indicate "yes", "no", or a neutral attitude. Such a development may suggest increasing uncertainty regarding the nuances of the issue under investigation. These results may also suggest the need for further studies to understand the media effect that has contributed to this change in response distribution, including any changes in external conditions, level of information, or changes in societal norms and values. It is important to

analyse the context surrounding this data to accurately identify the causes of such changes and their potential implications for the topic under investigation.

The thesis analyses the barchart below from the content analysis, where the number of articles is shown on the vertical axis and the articles' opinions on the horizontal axis, the results from period 1 are shown in figure 15 below.

Figure 15

And for period 2 illustrated in the barchart below (see figure 16).

Figure 16

When analysing the tables from the content analysis in detail, the results for period 1 and period 2 are presented in contrasting ways. For the first period, an attitude trend is seen, while the tables for the second period show an oppositely directed attitude trend. This indicates a shift in coverage. This observation clearly confirms the discrepancy identified in the ordinal study and this pattern is significantly repeated in the nominal study. This repetition of discrepancy between the two survey types indicates a robustness in the observed changes over the periods analysed, highlighting the importance of further analysis to understand the underlying causes of these differences.

We can only speculate about the reasons for such associations in time, but we cannot rule out the possibility that media are actually more Influential in certain ways at times of crisis (McQuail, 1994, p. 333)

As McQuail describes, we cannot ignore that this difference in media portrayal over the two periods studied will have an effect on the population. Using the codebook function to objectively review the data, it appears that the significant changes in the cumulative percentages between the two measurement periods indicate a significant shift in media attitudes or perceptions over time (McQuail, 1994, pp. 333-338). In the first period, there was an overwhelming consensus in favour of the "pro Israel" category, as defined in section 3.1.2, with 82% of the media expressing this opinion, compared to 2% for "pro Palestine" and 2% for "pro Hamas". In contrast, the data from the second period shows an inverse distribution of responses, with 54% expressing support for "pro Palestine" and 6% for Hamas. This could indicate significant changes in relation to the topic under investigation, the intention of the media and how they choose to describe the topic. McQuail's concept of "facilitate change" can be seen in the context of media coverage being seen to influence public perception in one direction, whether this was intentional on the part of the media or not (McQuail, 1994, pp. 333-338).

The drench hypothesis originally proposed that particular media items show strong and immediate media effects (Thomas, 2022, p. 403).

As Thomas explains, while certain media activities can have an immediate effect, when we look at the media coverage of the conflict during the two periods studied, it is characterised by a constant and overwhelming amount of articles, indicating a 'drench effect'. This type of effect occurs when massive media exposure, rather than a gradual influx of information, has the potential to significantly influence public attitudes. It is therefore relevant to investigate whether there is a measurable correlation between changes in media coverage and public attitudes, i.e. whether the drench effect is fleeting, fading or far reaching

This type of effect occurs when massive media exposure, rather than a gradual influx of information, has the potential to significantly influence public attitudes. It is therefore relevant to investigate whether there is a measurable correlation between changes in media coverage and public attitudes, i.e. whether the drench effect is fleeting, fading, or far-reaching.

(Thomas, 2022, pp. 403; 405-410). These media effect patterns will be explored further in the following analysis of the survey.

5.1.2 Analysing survey data

How have people's attitudes changed within the same periods? The demographic data such as gender, age and education provide insights into social structures that can influence research results. Gender and age are basic categories, while education often indicates socioeconomic status. This information is important because it provides a deeper insight into the respondents' background and helps place their attitudes in a measurable context. Although education in Denmark is state-funded, it can still reflect socioeconomic status, as education and career choices are often influenced by family resources and background. Overall, this data helps analyse patterns and trends across different population groups.

Analysing the nominal scale variables on the gender distribution of the 130 participants, an almost equal distribution is observed with 50.8% women and 49.2% men. Although there was an option to identify as non-binary, no one chose this designation, which means that non-binary people are not represented in this study. However, the balanced gender ratio between the two genders represented contributes to a more nuanced understanding of the population's reactions and attitudes (see Appendix 13).

When analysing the ratio scale variables representing age distributions, we see that the 15-20 age group represents 19.2% of the respondents, the 20-30 age group represents a percentage of 38.5% of the group of participants, the 30-40 group has 23.8% of the participants, the 40-50 group is represented with 15.4% and the 50+ group with 3.1%. Due to the fact that the participants themselves chose to participate in the survey, there has been no selection, and therefore I cannot generalise from the responses, but note that these groupings were present when the survey was conducted during the given period (see Appendix 13).

When analysing the cross-tabulations of respondents' attitudes towards the conflict on 7 October 2023, the survey includes 130 participants. When I examine their immediate reactions to the attack on Israel on 7 October 2023, the frequencies show that 55 participants (42.3%) were shocked, 54 participants (41.5%) were not surprised, and 16 participants (12.3%) remained neutral. These results indicate an almost equal split between those who were shocked and those who were not surprised, which may reflect different levels of anticipation or preparation for such events among the population. What is notable here is the difference in the number of women and men who were neutral about the conflict on 7 October 2023. 13 women, mainly in the 20-30 age group, were neutral. In comparison, only 3 men took a neutral stance, all in the 40+ age group. No men under the age of 40 remained neutral, indicating that almost all men had a clear position on the events of 7 October 2023 (see Figure 17).

**What was your immediate reaction to the news of Hamas' attack on Israel on 7 October 2023?
Which age group do you belong to? How do you identify in terms of gender? Crosstabulation**

Count			Which age group do you belong to?					Total
How do you identify in terms of gender?			15-20	20-30	30-40	40-50	50+	
Women	What was your reaction to the news of Hamas' attack on Israel on 7 October 2023?	Other	0	0	1	1	0	2
		Shocked	7	12	5	3	0	27
		Not Surprised	6	11	5	2	0	24
		Neutral	2	4	3	3	1	13
	Total		15	27	14	9	1	66
Man	What was your reaction to the news of Hamas' attack on Israel on 7 October 2023?	Other	2	0	1	0	0	3
		Shocked	5	13	8	0	2	28
		Not Surprised	3	10	8	9	0	30
		Neutral	0	0	0	2	1	3
	Total		10	23	17	11	3	64
Total	What was your reaction to the news of Hamas' attack on Israel on 7 October 2023?	Other	2	0	2	1	0	5
		Shocked	12	25	13	3	2	55
		Not Surprised	9	21	13	11	0	54
		Neutral	2	4	3	5	2	16
	Total		25	50	31	20	4	130

Figure 17

When asked who the participants sympathised with most immediately after the attack, 91 participants (70%) indicated that they sympathised most with Israel. This high level of sympathy for Israel immediately after the attack may be a result of media coverage that often initially focuses on the victims and the immediate impact of such attacks. I will refer to this as "news learning" as I observe short-term cognitive effects of media exposure, where respondents quickly assimilate and react to information from the news media (McQuail, 1994, pp. 336-338). This media influence is further supported by the fact that 66.2% of participants indicated that they perceived the media coverage to be sympathetic towards Israel. This indicates that a large proportion of respondents read the media content as sympathetic to Israel's cause (see Appendix 13).

This is evident in the frequency model, which shows the number of respondents (91), represented as units on the left vertical axis, who expressed sympathy for Israel in the initial phase of the conflict, as illustrated in Figure 18 below, where the vertical axis the number of the 130 respondents answering each category and the horizontal axis represents attitudes (see Appendix 13).

Figure 18

When asked whether their views on the conflict have changed since 7 October, we see a significant shift in sympathy. 70 participants (53.8%), of which 22.3% are men and 31.5% women, indicate that they now have more sympathy for Palestine, which is a significant change from their initial sympathy for Israel immediately after the attack. This shift may indicate that additional information and news developments after the initial incident have influenced participants' views. It also shows how the continued evolution of media coverage can shape and change public perceptions over time (see Figure 19)

Figure 19

Analysing the frequency table of sympathies at the beginning of the conflict shows that 70% of respondents expressed sympathy for Israel, while 23.1% (30 participants) supported Palestine. This distribution indicates a significant preponderance of support for Israel in the

initial phase of the conflict. When I take a closer look at the survey analysing the personal factors that influenced the respondents' attitudes towards the conflict, it turns out that 23.1% of the participants maintain that their attitudes are based solely on their personal values, unaffected by external influences. This 23.1% can thus be equated to the 23.1% who supported Palestine at the beginning of the conflict, as a close reading of the survey's Excel spreadsheet confirms. This finding highlights how deeply embedded values shape the formation of human attitudes and sympathies, indicating that a significant minority of the participants base their opinions on internal, perhaps deeply rooted beliefs rather than the external information sources (see Appendix 14) (Rokeach, 1973, pp. 5-17; 23-24; 34-37; 82-83; 110-113; 263).

A close reading of the data from the frequency model on attitude changes during the course of the conflict reveals that 35.4% of respondents indicated that their attitudes remained unchanged. Among those whose attitudes did not change, 23.1% are part of this larger group. This group initially sympathised with Palestine and maintained their views due to personal values. The difference between these groups is 12.3 percentage points. There is a further discrepancy of 4.7%, which corresponds to the group that initially supported Israel due to similar values and have not changed their views either (Appendix 14). These results were found after further manual review of the Excel sheet (see Appendix 15). This is particularly noteworthy as it reflects a deeply rooted personal value orientation that has proven robust to external influences, and the result is striking as it indicates a stability in personal values that are often formed early in life and are resistant to change despite changing external circumstances, as Rokeach, Bryman and McCombs have all highlighted (Rokeach, 1973, pp. 5-17; 23-24; 34-37; 82-83; 110-113; 263) (McCombs, 2014, p. 105).

When I compare the results from the content analysis, where 82% of articles in the first period had a positive view of Israel, with the results from the second period, where 60% reported positively on Palestine and Hamas, I notice a significant shift in attitude. Compared to the survey results, it is striking that a significant proportion of respondents who were sympathetic to Israel in October 2023 support Palestine in May 2024. This coincidence in time between the media and the respondents' shift in attitude indicates that the shift can be attributed to media coverage. Both McQuail's concept of "news learning" and Thomas' "recency effect" explain how more recent information has the greatest impact on recipients' perceptions and attitudes. As previously mentioned, the study is based on a sample of 100 articles from selected newspapers, and this sample shows a significant shift in respondents' attitudes over time, which clearly shows that media coverage has a significant impact on changes in public opinion (Thomas, 2022, p. 405) (McQuail, 1994, pp. 337-338).

Furthermore, this is also supported by McQuail's idea that media coverage can create complex reactions, such as increased uncertainty or a form of "moral panic," due to the many subsequent demonstrations for Palestine and against Israel etc, when an issue becomes more complex or controversial, it can therefore be considered a "collective reaction".

Furthermore, this aligns with McQuail's idea that media coverage can induce complex reactions, such as heightened uncertainty or a form of "moral panic," evidenced by the

numerous subsequent demonstrations for Palestine and against Israel. When an issue becomes more complex or controversial, it may thus be viewed as a “collective reaction.”

This phenomenon can largely be attributed to all types of media including social media (SoMe) (McQuail, 1994, pp. 333-338) (Skyum, 2024) (Søgaard, 2024).

News learning: the short-term cognitive effect of exposure to mass media news, as measured by tests of audience recall, recognition or comprehension (McQuail, 1994, p. 337).

Against this background, it is worth noting that the change in media content from the content analysis follows the changes in attitudes clearly seen in the survey. McQuail explains this by stating that media content, both news and entertainment, gives us insight into different norms and values, which can influence our worldview, and that this exposure can lead to changing perceptions depending on the media content and its agenda (McQuail, 1994, pp. 332-335). In relation to this, it can be argued that the media's role in shaping the public's perception of the conflict is very much in play here. McCombs also emphasises that agenda-setting assigns the news media a central role in putting issues on the public agenda. It is clear that respondents are not only reacting to their surroundings, but very much to the shifting sympathies of media content. Especially when the perspective of media coverage changes, this change is reflected in respondents' attitudes (McCombs, 2014, p. 6; 24; 77).

The media can influence people's views through framing, selective exposure and repetitive narratives, which can change or reinforce underlying attitudes. This can be considered an expression of media effectiveness. The observed change in respondents' perception of the situation between the two periods can thus be seen as a result of media influence, where personal values are affected, illustrating the tension between fixed personal beliefs and flexible attitudes that are susceptible to external influences. It can also be seen as an expression of a "collective reaction," as the group reacts similarly to media influence, as they are likely to experience the same effects in a common context (McQuail, 1994, pp. 331-333; 336-338).

When analysing the factors that influenced participants' attitudes towards the conflict, I see that 74 participants (56.9%) cite media coverage as a significant influence. This emphasises the strong influence of media content on public attitudes. A further 16.2% (21 participants) cite social media as the primary influence, reflecting the growing role of digital platforms in information dissemination and opinion formation. Furthermore, 53.8% (70 participants) have changed their opinion on the conflict, of which 59 (84.2%) are under 30 years old. It is also notable that of the 70 participants who have changed their attitudes due to the media, only 11 are over 30 years old. This indicates that younger age groups are more susceptible to the influence of media coverage, which is confirmed by Rokeach's theory, which emphasises that young people are more likely to be influenced by the media (Rokeach, 1973, pp. 5-17; 23-24; 34-37; 82-83; 110-113; 263) (McCombs, 2014, p. 105).

Overall, the survey shows that while there was initially a predominant sympathy for Israel after the 7 October attack, sympathy has since shifted in favour of Palestine among a significant proportion of participants. This shift can be partly attributed to media coverage, which many participants cite as a crucial factor in their opinion formation. The demographic

distribution of gender and education among the participants also provides a nuanced picture of the target group in the study, which contributes to a deeper understanding of the complex dynamics of public opinion formation (see Appendix 14) (McQuail, 1994, pp. 332-333).

The Thomas media effect pattern that best characterises the impact over the two periods is the 'far-reaching' effect. This is because the effect is not merely temporary or diminishing but instead demonstrates a profound and lasting influence on respondents' attitudes over time. When a significant proportion of respondents change from sympathising with Israel to supporting Palestine, and this change is attributed to the shifting focus of media coverage, there is an impact that has managed to change fundamental perceptions and values in a larger proportion of the population. This points to an effect that has lasting consequences and can therefore be described as far-reaching (Thomas, 2022, pp. 405-410).

This finding is in line with the theories of McQuail and McCombs, who emphasise how the media not only reflect but also shape public perceptions of issues and conflicts, especially when media content changes over time and influences recipients' attitudes in a pervasive way (McQuail, 1994, pp. 331-332) (McCombs, 2014, pp. 105-106).

As Thomas explains, certain media activities can have an immediate effect, when I analyse the media coverage in the two periods studied, they have been characterised by a constant and overwhelming amount of articles about the conflict, indicating a "drench effect". The massive media coverage, rather than a gradual influx of information, may therefore have had a direct impact on public attitudes (Thomas, 2022, pp. 403; 405-410).

Hjarvad's medialisatation theory is in line with McQuail, Thomas and McCombs' descriptions of media effects, particularly in relation to how media can shape and change societal perceptions and attitudes over time. Medialisatation refers to the process in which the media becomes integrated into and influences different areas of society, leading to a change in social relations, cultural norms and political processes, thus Hjarvad's theory supports the idea that the media are not just neutral disseminators of information, but active actors that can influence public attitudes and values. When the media shifts focus or framing, as described in the analysis of respondents' attitudinal shifts, it is an example of the power of medialisatation to influence societal processes and individual perceptions (Hjarvad, 2009, pp. 5-9; 13-14; 29-33).

Medialisatation theory highlights how media content can influence and change societal structures by shaping the way people perceive and interact with the world. Shifts in media content often result in changes in public attitudes, exemplifying the influence of medialisatation. This understanding aligns with the theories of McQuail and McCombs, which emphasise the ability of media to set agendas and influence attitudes over time (Hjarvad, 2009, pp. 13-14; 29-33).

The variation in results between the two survey periods can therefore be explained by the media effect, which influences public attitudes. Changes in the intensity and angle of media coverage can significantly shape public perceptions, highlighting the power of the media to influence public opinion (McQuail, 1994, pp. 350-351). To further understand these shifts in

attitudes, in-depth interviews could be useful to uncover the underlying factors driving the changes (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015, pp. 45-55).

5.1.3 Qualitative interview results

How are these changes in attitude expressed qualitatively in an interview? On 2 June 2024, I conducted two interviews in Copenhagen: one with an informant I call Kasper, which took place at Café Oven Vande, and the other with an informant I call Harald, which took place in his apartment on Sankt Annæ Gade. The purpose was to shed light on their attitudes to the conflict between Hamas/Palestine and Israel and their experience of the media coverage. The transcripts and M4A files of these interviews can be found in appendices 16a-c (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015, p. 163).

In the survey, I had asked the respondents in the explanatory text to reply by email if they wanted to participate in a short interview about the topic and from these, I selected two respondents to interview. Kasper and I met at Café Oven Vande in Christianshavn, which was chosen for practical reasons, as I was scheduled to interview another respondent nearby afterwards. The two respondents were selected from five volunteers in the survey group based on their availability that Sunday. As a precaution, I refrained from informing the others before the interviews were finalised and approved (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015, pp. 157-158).

After further contact with Kasper, the café was deemed a suitable meeting place. Kasper, a man in his forties with a higher education, and I began with an informal conversation to create a relaxed atmosphere. I explained the purpose and procedure of the interview, including the recording, as agreed, which contributed to the respondent's comfort (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015, pp. 157-158).

I used a transcript of the questions to ensure structure and avoid repetition and thus maintain a good flow throughout the process. When Kasper confirmed that he was ready, I started the interview with the recorder switched on (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015, pp. 159-162).

Kasper had not travelled in the Israel-Palestine area in recent years. He described his immediate reaction to the Hamas attack on 7 October 2023 as shock and found the incident horrific.

I was almost in shock; I thought it was as horrible as anything can be! Well, of course I sympathised with the Jews and Israel, they were the ones who were attacked, it was so barbaric and terrible, so I definitely sympathised with them (see Appendix 16a) (Kasper, 2024).

He initially expressed strong sympathy for Israel and the Jewish victims, whom he saw as the primary victims of the Hamas attack. He felt that the media coverage in the days following the attack was sufficient in describing the violent events and the innocent victims. Kasper's

attitude towards the conflict was largely shaped by his reading of newspapers, social media, and his use of radio and TV.

Well, I've kept up with the newspapers and I go to the library and read many different newspapers, I've read a lot on Facebook, many people have written about it and of course there's also radio and TV (see Appendix 16a) (Kasper, 2024).

Over time, however, his viewpoint evolved as the media coverage of the conflict evolved. By the end of May 2024, he had become more sympathetic to the Palestinians, seeing them as the primary victims because of the images and stories he had seen and heard about.

Well, there it's even more, it's become even more apparent what the Palestinians are up against, and that some are even talking about genocide, and I've also read about the very aggressive settlers in the West Bank, so I think the Palestinians have it tough (see Appendix 16a) (Kasper, 2024).

He found the media coverage in April 2024 focused more on Palestine and their victims, which contributed to his shift in attitude.

I've probably got more sympathy for the Palestinians, you know, I've seen pictures of killed children and some pretty horrible things throughout the Gaza Strip, so I've got more sympathy for the Palestinians and their cause (see appendix 24) (Kasper, 2024) .

Kasper identifies himself as male and has a higher education. The interview ended with a thank you for his participation.

Harald had also not visited Israel-Palestine in recent years. His reaction to the news of the Hamas attack was one of dismay, and he initially sympathised with Israel because of the severity of the terrorist attack. He assessed the media coverage in the first week after the attack as violent and informative, with general support for Israel.

Yes, how do I judge it to have been? I think it was quite intense and informative. I think most of what they talked about was about Israel. They supported them in one way or another, Israel... Well, that's because you hear so much about genocide and things like that. And it's horrible what's going on at the moment (see appendix 16b) (Harald, 2024) .

Harald's attitude was influenced by the reported descriptions of the attack on Israel that he heard about through newspapers, TV and radio.

It's mostly from, well, newspapers and news on TV and radio (see appendix 16b) (Harald, 2024).

His attitude changed over time as the media focus had shifted from Israel to Hamas/Palestine, making him more aware of this aspect of the conflict, and so his attitude changed too.

It probably is, because, as I said earlier, there are so many terrible things happening in Gaza and the country or enclave is almost in ruins and there are lots of children and women who are being killed, and you hear a lot about what's going on being genocide (see Appendix 16b) (Harald, 2024).

Harald was particularly struck by the term "genocide," which he had initially read used to describe Hamas' attacks on Israel and subsequently used to describe Israel's defence against Hamas. Harald identifies himself as male and has a medium-level education. The interview ended with a thank you to Harald for his participation

Through the interviews, it becomes clear how both Kasper and Harald initially had sympathy for Israel as a result of Hamas' attacks, but over time they changed their stance due to the changing media coverage, from having a stance at the beginning of the conflict that they were "pro-Israel", to after six months having changed their stance in favour of Hamas/Palestine.

5.1.4 Results analysis

The thesis utilises the mixed methods Explanatory Sequential design by combining both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods, such as content analysis, surveys and interviews. This provides a broader and more nuanced understanding of the topic under investigation. Triangulation is used in the thesis to increase the validity of the study by cross-checking the results from different methods, which reduces the risk of bias and ensures more reliable results.

The content analysis of the 100 articles shows a clear change in attitudinal representation between the two periods, this is particularly prominent in articles written by the same journalist over the two periods, where diametrically opposing views on the topic in question are observed. This variation can be attributed to factors such as political, labour demands and societal shifts that may have influenced journalists' opinions, such as demonstrations against Israel.

Changes in media coverage are clearly seen to have a "drench effect," as the media flow is constant. The change in angle can thus also be seen to significantly influence public perspectives and emphasise the media's influence on public opinion, clearly indicating that the effect is "far reaching" (Thomas, 2022, pp. 403; 405-410).

Taking the case of the thesis and the media coverage of it in the two periods analysed, with the date of the outbreak of the conflict as $t+1$ and until the end of each period as $t+n$, I can observe a constant media flow. From 7 October 2023 and one week onwards, there is a constant media flow in the first period, and similarly, the media flow is constant in the second period, which begins on 7 April 2024. When I examine the media flow in the period between the first and second period, the intensity does not decrease either. This suggests that the effect is a drench effect with a stable media flow. Regardless of whether I had chosen an earlier or later start point, such as $t+4$, and adjusted the time for the endpoint, $t+n$, the pattern would remain constant. This confirms that the media effect observed in this study is indeed a drench effect (Thomas, 2022, pp. 403; 405-410).

Subsequently, I can analyse how the individual's response has been and thus assess outcome ti . Then I can test whether there is a γ_1 effect, and finally assess whether this is

related to the media element, i.e. whether Thomas' criteria for Outcome $t_i = \gamma_1 \times (\text{media item})^{t_i^3}$ are met, and whether this is an immediate effect, i.e. a drench effect (Thomas, 2022, pp. 403-406)

When I analyse the results from the two interviews, it appears that both informant "Kasper" and informant "Harald" were immediately affected by the media's framing of the conflict. In the first period, both informants endorsed the media's perspective and sympathised with the views highlighted by the media. This fulfils Thomas' criteria for an immediate response, that there is a γ_1 effect, which further supports the news media's agenda-setting function, which refers to the media's role in identifying key issues and their ability to influence how important these issues are perceived in the public agenda (Thomas, 2022, pp. 403-406) (McCombs, 2014, p. 1).

Furthermore, I will investigate whether the effect is fleeting, fading or far reaching.

When I re-analyse the results from the two interviews, it becomes clear that both informants' attitudes changed over time, which they attribute to the changing media coverage. When the media coverage changed from being pro-Israel at the beginning of the conflict to favouring Hamas/Palestine after six months, the informants also experienced a personal shift in attitude, which they attribute to media influence. From this I can interpret that this is not just a fleeting effect, as the media effect has a strong hold on the informants and I do not feel that the effect is fleeting as both informants express how the media effect changes their personal perceptions of the conflict, so this is a "far reaching" effect (Thomas, 2022, pp. 403-410).

When I compare the content analysis, survey and interview results, I see that 82% of the articles in the first period were "pro-Israel", while in the second period the distribution was 54% "pro-Palestine" and 6% "pro-Hamas". I observe that both the informants and the participants in the survey were affected by this media shift, as their attitudes changed in line with the media coverage. This again emphasises that this is a "drench effect" and that it is "far reaching" (Thomas, 2022, pp. 403; 405-410).

This also indicates that the media exhibits significant changes in relation to the topic studied, which may be due to the personal or professional experiences of journalists or media managers, which ultimately determine how the topic is chosen to be presented (McQuail, 1994, pp. 333-338).

Analysing these aspects is crucial to understanding the changes in public attitudes between the two survey periods. The comparison of the results from the quantitative content analysis and the intercoder reliability test data shows that the differences in the distribution of responses between the content analysis results and the results produced by "Lasse" and "Kristian" are minimal, indicating high consistency in the interpretations. Both test subjects agree with my judgements and the level of agreement is clearly above 85%, which should be the ceiling for a credible study. Further analysis shows that when this data is compared to the general result from the larger study, the test subjects effectively support the main

³ (Thomas, 2022, p. 403)

result, indicating that there is code consensus, i.e. agreement between the results I have arrived at and the results the test subjects have arrived at (see Appendix 5e).

This consistency of results between the test subjects and the full study suggests that the methodology used is robust and reliable, which is essential for drawing valid conclusions about the nature and extent of the media effect. It also illustrates the effectiveness of the coding system and methodological approach used to capture consistent patterns in the data.

When I compare the results from the quantitative part of the study with the qualitative part of the study, I see that the two studies support each other by highlighting the connection between methodological robustness and the concrete effects of media influence on individual attitudes.

The quantitative part highlights a consistency of results between test subjects and the content analysis indicates a robust and reliable methodology. This methodological reliability is essential for drawing valid conclusions about the extent of the media effect. If the methodology can detect consistent patterns in the data across different groups and subjects, it reinforces confidence that the results found are not random but actually represent real trends.

The qualitative part of the study illustrates specific examples of how media influence can change individual attitudes over time. Interviews with informants Kasper and Harald show that their attitudes changed from supporting Israel to supporting Hamas/Palestine as a result of changes in media coverage. This shift from pro-Israel to pro-Hamas/Palestine coverage shows the power of media coverage to influence public perceptions on complex conflicts.

Individual response: the process by which individuals change, or resist change, following exposure to messages designed to influence attitude, knowledge or behaviour (McQuail, 1994, p. 335).

McQuail explains how individual response refers to how individuals either change or maintain their attitudes, knowledge or behaviour after being exposed to influential messages. This process is central to the study of media effects and communication theory as it illustrates how people respond to attempts to change their perceptions or behaviour. Messages can be designed to change attitudes, reinforce existing beliefs or counteract resistance to change (McQuail, 1994, pp. 335-338).

According to McQuail's theory, Kasper and Harald's changing attitudes towards the conflict can be seen as a clear example of how media coverage has influenced their individual responses. Their individual response is reflected in how their views have evolved in opposite directions over time, emphasising the power of the media to shape and change public attitudes, regardless of their prior attitudes, experiences and social context (McQuail, 1994, pp. 335-338).

Again, Thomas' theory of the "drench" and "far reaching" effects is confirmed, which also emphasises McQuail's media effect theory, as we see both a "media power" and a "media

effectiveness," as their communication goals, in this case the change of attitude in the message, are seen fulfilled by the immediate response of respondents/informants as the media changes the message's attitude. This illustrates how media coverage can change attitudes towards conflicts in opposite directions over time and confirms Hjarvad's medialisatation theory of the active role of media in societal transformation. It also supports McQuail's intentionality concepts of news learning and distribution of knowledge and McCombs' agenda-setting theory, as media shifts clearly influence which issues the population considers important through respond (Thomas, 2022, pp. 403; 405-410) (McQuail, 1994, pp. 332-333; 335-341) (Hjarvad, 2009, pp. 32-33) (McCombs, 2014, pp. 1-2; 100)

As further confirmation of the thesis findings, Hjarvad & Kristensen's article also demonstrates the ability of media content to influence perceptions in certain situations through agenda-setting and framing, thus confirming the thesis findings. Hjarvad & Kristensen's article also supports the theoretical framework on which this thesis is based by analysing how media shifts in attitude and framing affect respondents' perceptions and attitudes (Hjarvad & Kristensen, 2014). Similarly, my thesis shows how media coverage of the conflict between Hamas and Israel reflects this trend of medialisatation where the media actively shapes and changes society's perception.

6. Conclusion

Through quantitative and qualitative analyses of the media coverage regarding the Israel-Hamas conflict, this thesis has uncovered a clear connection between the media's portrayal of the conflict's topics and public perception. The results show how the media image has changed between these periods and how the media coverage creates significant shifts in public attitudes over time. The quantitative content analysis has demonstrated how the media shifts its bias and how this influences respondents' attitudes towards the conflict. In particular, McQuail's concepts of "news learning" and Thomas' "recency effect" have been used to explain how new information quickly influences recipients' perceptions (McQuail, 1994, pp. 336-338) (Thomas, 2022, p. 405).

Furthermore, the thesis supports theories about the media's agenda-setting role and ability to shape public priorities. This is evident in the shifting media coverage, where the attitude towards the conflict changed from being pro-Israel to being more sympathetic towards Palestine. The thesis thus demonstrates the media's ability to not only report, but also to influence and in some cases directly shape public discourse, which has profound consequences for both individual and collective perceptions of political conflict (McCombs, 2014, pp. 1-2; 100) (McQuail, 1994, pp. 327-328; 332-335).

Using McQuail's concepts of "news learning" and "collective reaction" and "individual response", the thesis highlights that recipients not only reflect the media content, but that their attitudes can change significantly through exposure to news stories and their framing. Thomas' theory of the 'drench effect' explains how intensive media coverage can have lasting effects on attitude formation, and this is evident in the thesis findings, where a majority of respondents have changed their views over time. This persistent impact can be seen as an expression of Thomas' far-reaching media influence (McQuail, 1994, pp. 336-338) (Thomas, 2022, pp. 405; 407-408).

Furthermore, the thesis' qualitative analyses confirm Hjarvad's medialisatation theory, which shows how the media actively changes societal perceptions and structures. By integrating both quantitative and qualitative data, the thesis has provided an in-depth understanding of how media effects operate in complex political conflicts and how these effects can be shaped by both political and societal dynamics. Furthermore, the thesis findings confirm Hjarvad and Kristensen's conclusion that media content can influence perceptions through agenda-setting and framing, further validating the thesis findings (Hjarvad, 2009, pp. 5-7) (Hjarvard & Kristensen, 2014).

In summary, the thesis concludes that the media's changing framing of conflicts has a profound and lasting effect on public attitudes, that these media effects are clearly seen to alter individuals' perceptions of specific issues, again supporting the theories of McQuail, McCombs, Thomas and Hjarvad on media power and its influence on public discourse.

7. Perspective

Finally, the thesis will put the issue into perspective in relation to current societal challenges and discuss how the media can contribute to information and promote pluralism. The rationale is that the results of the thesis should not only be seen in the context of war or disasters, but should be seen in a perspective based on a comparison of the case studied with other cases

Looking back at the case of the conflict between Hamas and Israel, for example, the Foreign Minister speaks out first on 20 October 2023 and then on 4 May 2024, first expressing support for Israel and condemnation of Hamas (Mach, 2023), and later, in an article in Information, criticising Israeli war crimes in Gaza (Information, 2024). This illustrates how the government's position changes between the two periods. Already in the op-ed in Politiken on 18 October 2023, it can be seen how certain groups are trying to put political pressure on the government, including Enhedslisten's Trine Pertou Mach (Mach, 2023).

At the same time, in October 2023, students at the Academy of Fine Arts were observed to have put up posters declaring support for Palestine (see Appendix 17). Subsequently, DR's teletext TV reported that Middle Eastern Hamas supporters were chasing Jews in the streets of Copenhagen (see Appendix 18). On 18 January 2024, DR2 broadcast the programme "The Debate" focusing on the Hamas/Israel conflict under the headline "Is Gaza just the beginning?". During the programme, Kashif Ahmad from the Danish Liberal Party stated that "as long as Palestine is not free, no one is free". This statement can be interpreted as a general support for Palestine and the Middle East, while several participants argued that it could be perceived as an indirect legitimisation of Hamas' fight against Israel (see Appendix 18a-e).

DR's coverage from May 2024 supports this trend, where a Jewish PhD student was met with threatening battle cries from the tent camp demonstration, including slogans such as "no to Nakba - globalise the intifada" and "there is only one solution, intifada revolution" (Trolle, 2024). This emphasises the same tensions that I myself observed during a pro-Palestinian demonstration in the spring of 2024 in the streets of Copenhagen, where several Arab/Palestinian participants repeatedly shouted "al-mawt al yahud, al-mawt al Israel" (death to the Jews, death to Israel) (see Appendix 19).

Although in October 2023 the media reports the attack on Israel with predominant sympathy for Israel, there are indications that certain political groupings already have a clear anti-Israel stance prior to the attack. The Foreign Minister condemns these attacks early on, but by May 2024, he has changed course.

8. Three other perspective examples of the media's use of framing

In a completely different context, you can experience something similar, also as a result of the media and science framing and presenting flawed scientific studies as facts. In an article from DR by Jeppe Knudsen, the joint international research around the study "Population genomics of the Viking world" is presented in this way. A project involving 85 researchers, in which Eske Willerslev was one of three main researchers who took part in a DNA study on the Vikings, which has been criticised for exaggerating and distorting the research results in order to create populism and sensation (Willerslev, 2019) (Knudsen, 2020). The DR article, based on an interview with Willerslev, ignores the researchers' scientific reservations, such as the use of terms like "likely" and "suggest", which signal that the conclusions are not definitive. This lack of nuance in communication creates misunderstandings and distorts public understanding of the research. Another point of criticism is that the research and the scientific article do not distinguish between free Vikings and slaves, which means that all DNA is treated as Viking DNA (Willerslev, 2019). This leads to an overestimation of the genetic diversity among the Vikings and thus distorts the understanding of their culture. Furthermore, the article does not take into account the gene TMEM131, which is linked to adaptation to cold climates and is common among northern Europeans (Jakobsen, 2018). This gene is an important factor in separating Vikings from southern populations in genetic analyses. Academic criticism of Willerslev's research highlights the need for a more nuanced approach to DNA studies that recognises social structures and the structure of Viking society, including the central role played by slaves. Genetic findings should always be interpreted in a broader context of culture and social hierarchies to provide a more accurate picture of Viking heritage and influence (see Appendix 29).

From a broader perspective, we see that the media frames the coverage of pollution by shifting the focus from industry to agriculture and away from the explosive population growth in regions like the Middle East and Africa. At the same time, the discussion of diversity is directed towards a few selected regions rather than on a global scale, while the industry's use of advertising to promote overconsumption is downplayed. Instead, the West's consumption of animal-based foods is framed as a possible main cause of pollution (Infomedia.dk, Klimaprofessor: Bestanden af køer er meget passende i dag, 2023) (Berlingske, 2022) (Krogbeck, 2024) (Infomedia.dk, 2022) (Microsoft, 2024)

These examples illustrate how industry, media, political actors and science shape public perception and contribute to the debate on framing complex issues. As Thomas Hedin from "TjekDet" says: "lies and false images can still have a big impact because they incite users and those feelings stick." (Politiken, 2023) These three very different perspectives highlight an unfortunate evolution in media coverage and the importance of exploring the factors that continue to contribute to shifting attitudes, including changes in the political context, the media's role in covering these cases and changes in international perspectives. An in-depth analysis of these aspects will be crucial to understanding how and why public attitudes can change so significantly between the two study periods, for example.

In conclusion, the observations of this thesis thus highlight the pressing need for and the critical importance of further research into the influence of media effects on the formation of attitudes among societal groups.

9. Bibliography

(n.d.).

- Berlingske. (2022, January 23). *Overpopulation in Africa and the Middle East forces Europe to change course*. Retrieved from www.berlingske.dk; Olesen, Gunnar: <https://www.berlingske.dk/kronikker/overbefolkning-i-afrika-og-mellemoesten-tvinger-europa-til-ny-kurs>
- Bryman, A. (2016). *Social Research Methods*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Bryman, A. (2021). *Social Research Methods*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Dimitrova, D., & Strömbäck, J. (2005, October). Mission Accomplished? Framing of the Iraq War in the Elite Newspapers in Sweden and the United States. *Sage Journals Vol 67 Issue 5*.
- Ekstra-Bladet. (2023, October 10). Will kill hostages. *Ritzau*, p. 27.
- Elmelund, R. (2024, January 19). *Information.dk*. Retrieved from [Information.dk](https://www.information.dk/kultur/2024/01/katherine-diez-kulturelle-kapital-krakelerer-afsloeringer-afskrift-andres-tekster): <https://www.information.dk/kultur/2024/01/katherine-diez-kulturelle-kapital-krakelerer-afsloeringer-afskrift-andres-tekster>
- Eskjær, M. F., & Helles, R. (2021). *Quantitative Content Analysis*. Copenhagen; Frederiksberg: Samfundslitteratur.
- Fairclough, N. (2010). *Critical Discourse Analysis*. London/New York: Routledge.
- From, R. (2024, February 1). *Berlingske.dk*. Retrieved from https://www.berlingske.dk/kommentatorer/hvis-man-for-alvor-fryder-sig-over-katherine-diez-nu-har-man-nok?utm_source=social&utm_medium=facebook&utm_content=post&fbclid=IwAR2XRf7jWpvgIAMgRQkZSs010vS4RU4EXBQT-QD-pk1fGGjmVgylhvcCQbg_aem_AcDZzslgKFwjUcxTd01-mz
- Guldbrandsen, I. T., & Just, S. N. (2020). Strategic communication as process. In S. N. Ib T. Guldbrandsen, *Strategising Communication Theory and practice* (p. 430). Copenhagen: Samfundslitteratur.
- Gunter, B. (1984, October). Book review. *Social Science Information Studies, Volume 4, Issue 4*, pp. 334-336.
- Hjarvad, S. (2009, January 9). Retrieved from researchgate.net: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Stig-Hjarvard/publication/242683982_Samfundets_medialisering_En_teor_i_om_mediernes_forandring_af_samfund_og_kultur/links/55265ce10cf2ee9bad77c607/Samfundet-s-medialisering-En-teori-om-mediernes-forandring-af-samfund-og-
- Hjarvad, S., & Kristensen, N. N. (2014, April). When media of a small nation argue for war. *Sage Publications, Ltd*. pp. 51-69.

- Infomedia.dk (2022, June 18). Retrieved from <https://apps-infomedia-dk.ep.fjernadgang.kb.dk/mediemarkiv/link?articles=e8e44b25>
- Infomedia.dk (2023, March 11). *Climate professor: The population of cows is very appropriate today*. Retrieved from Thalbitzer, Frederik: <https://apps-infomedia-dk.ep.fjernadgang.kb.dk/mediemarkiv/link?articles=e9773e83>
- Information (2024, May 4). Løkke weighs risk of Israeli war crimes. *Gjerding, Sebastian; Andersen, Lasse Skou; Lykkeberg, Rune*.
- Jacobsen, P., & Møller, K. (2012). Good news: Libya and the Danish way of war. *Danish Foreign Policy Yearbook*, p. 106.
- Jakobsen, R. K. (2018, January 9). *From here came the first people in Scandinavia*. Retrieved from Infomedia.dk: <https://apps-infomedia-dk.ep.fjernadgang.kb.dk/mediemarkiv/link?articles=e6922f3f>
- Jantzen, C., Rasmussen, T. A., & Vetner, M. (2007). *Experience economy : angles on consumption*. Aalborg: Aalborg University Press.
- Jørgensen, T. F. (2023, October 10). 10 October 2023 Avisen Danmark (morgen) Section 1 Page 15 Tobias Farholt Jørgensen Ritzau ... 1009 words Id: e9e91ee7. *Avisen Danmark (morgen)* , p. Section 1 page 15.
- Jyllands-Posten. (2023, October 8). The enemy will pay a historical price. *Plougsgaard, Heidi*, p. 18.
- Kirkebæk-Johansson, L., & Trolle, J. S. (2024, May 6). *DR.dk*. Retrieved from <https://www.dr.dk/nyheder/seneste>: <https://www.dr.dk/nyheder/seneste/studerende-slaar-lejr-paa-koebenhavn-universitet-vi-kan-ikke-nojes-med-forsigtig>
- Kjær, G. A. (2024, February 4). *infomedia.dk*. Retrieved from <https://apps-infomedia-dk.ep.fjernadgang.kb.dk/mediemarkiv/link?articles=ea157c08>
- Knudsen, J. K. (2020, September 16). *Major study shatters Viking myths: They were neither fair-haired nor Scandinavian*. Retrieved from dr.dk: <https://www.dr.dk/nyheder/viden/kroppen/stor-undersogelse-smadrer-vikingemyter-de-var-hverken-lyshaarede-eller?fbclid=IwAR03knjremRP1x4MEvHag2g71CN3uaBV2sDRVNzMhDZ8cEuVY6Mss6g0-WU>
- Kosicki, G. M. (2006, January 1). Book review. *Public Opinion Quarterly, Volume 70, Issue 1*, pp. 124-127.
- Krogbeck, U. W. (2024, September 23). *AI, diversity, industry impact and reputation in society, and ESG are hot in the legal world*. Retrieved from www.danskeadvokater.dk: <https://danskeadvokater.dk/Nyheder.aspx?ID=19049&PID=92559&Action=1&Year=2024&NewsId=35241>

- Kühn, S. W. (2024, February 16). Retrieved from [berlingske.dk:
https://www.berlingske.dk/kultur/berlingskes-plagiatundersoegelse-af-katherine-diez-er-nu-afsluttet-her-er](https://www.berlingske.dk/kultur/berlingskes-plagiatundersoegelse-af-katherine-diez-er-nu-afsluttet-her-er)
- Kühn, S. W. (2024, February 16). *Berlingske.dk*. Retrieved from <https://www.berlingske.dk/kultur/berlingskes-plagiatundersoegelse-af-katherine-diez-er-nu-afsluttet-her-er>
- Kvale, S., & Brinkmann, S. (2015). *Interview*. Copenhagen: Hans Reitzels Forlag.
- Liisberg, K. B. (2018). *Lies and statins*. Copenhagen: Department of Media, Cognition and Communication; University of Copenhagen.
- Mach, T. P. (2023, October 10). *Folketinget*. Retrieved from <https://www.ft.dk/samling/20231/spoergsmaal/S122/index.htm>
- McCombs, M. (2014). *Setting the Agenda: Mass Media and Public Opinion*. Cambridge: Polite press.
- McQuail, D. (1994). *Mass communication theory An Introduction*. London Thousand Oaks New Delhi: Sage Publication Ltd.
- Microsoft. (2024, September 21). *End of support for Windows 10*. Retrieved from [www.microsoft.com: https://www.microsoft.com/da-dk/windows/end-of-support?r=1](https://www.microsoft.com/da-dk/windows/end-of-support?r=1)
- Mosco, V. (2009). Retrieved from [doi.org: https://doi.org/10.4135/978144627994](https://doi.org/10.4135/978144627994)
- Politiken. (2023, October 13). Social media spreads lies about Gaza at unprecedented speed and scale. *Bostrup, Jens*, p. 1.
- Quadflieg, S., Neuburg, K., & Nestler, S. (2022) *(Dis)Obedience in Digital Societies*. Bielefeld: Transcript Verlag.
- Rikke Peters. (2024, February 29). *Woke*. Copenhagen: Den Store Danske.
- Rokeach, M. (1973). *the nature of human values*. New York: The Free Press.
- Rosa, H. (2013). *Social Acceleration-A New Theory of Modernity*. New York: Columbia University Press. Retrieved from [degruyter: https://doi-org.ep.fjernadgang.kb.dk/10.7312/rosa14834](https://doi-org.ep.fjernadgang.kb.dk/10.7312/rosa14834)
- Singer, J. B. (2016, May 31). *Taylor & Francis Online*. Retrieved from <https://doi-org.ep.fjernadgang.kb.dk/10.1080/1461670X.2016.1186498>
- Sissons, H. (2006). *Practical Journalism: How to Write News*. London: SAGE Publication Ltd.
- Skyum, S. B. (2024, May 6). *The newspaper Denmark*.
- Søgaard, S. (2024, January 9). *Censorship at demo. Ekstra Bladet*.
- Sørensen, A. (2012). Retrieved from [pure.au.dk:
https://pure.au.dk/ws/files/56603501/S_rensen_2012d.pdf](https://pure.au.dk/ws/files/56603501/S_rensen_2012d.pdf)

- Thomas, F. (2022, May 11). A Methodological Framework for Analysing the Appearance and Duration of Media Effects. *Journal of Communication, Volume 72, Issue 3, June 2022, Pages 401-428*, p. 27.
- Trolle, J. S. (2024, May 18). <https://www.dr.dk/nyheder/indland>. Retrieved from dr.dk:
<https://www.dr.dk/nyheder/indland/joedisk-phd-studerende-blev-moedt-af-kampraab-fra-teltlejrdemonstration-opfattede>
- Vreese, C. H. (2005). News framing. *Information Design Journal; Identifying information and tenor in texts Vol 13 (1)*, pp. 51-62.
- Weiskopf, R. (2020). Retrieved from sagepub.com:
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/1350508419842708>
- Willerslev, E. (2019, July 17). *Population genomics of the Viking world*. Retrieved from BioRxiv.org: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1101/703405>
- Zuboff, S. (2015). Big other: Surveillance capitalism and the prospect of an information civilisation. *Journal of Information Technology*, pp. 75-89.